

InnoChain Network Journal #5

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and Architecture, Copenhagen

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FOREWORD

This fifth and final edition of the Innochain Journals presents the culminating events of Innochain: the Innochain exhibition, the Innochain conference and the Pre-VIVA course. All of these have been designed with the idea in mind, that a network of 15 projects shared between academic and industrial partners from all over Europe requires events which allow to review and conclude for the next steps in the individual projects and the general research of Innochain.

With many of the Innochain projects in the last part of their course the Innochain exhibition **PRACTICE FUTURES - BUILDING DESIGN FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE** provided a mean to gather resources and create a set of final demonstrators, which presented in many cases a stepping up from previous research trajectories and scales. The exhibition initiated and leverage not only the physical production of novel contributions. but served as well as means to test and refine the dissemination of the ESR projects to a wide array of audiences. The exhibition had a major impact internal to Innochain, to the industry partners and general public, as well as the hosting beneficiary at the Royal Academy of Fine Arts, Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation. Here the exhibition became a point of reference for students and teachers and was successfully used by the host to communicate, how research in Architecture and Technology can be performed, e.g to the Danish Minister for innovation, who paid a visit.

The Innochain conference **EXPANDING INFORMATION MODELLING FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE** contextualised the Innochain results in the interdisciplinary discourse of Information modelling. More than 150 participants took here part in a two-day inquiry in how this shared digital platform enables the emergence of a new hybrid practice. In here otherwise separate tools and methodologies of design, analysis and fabrication can intersect in a shared digital platform, which enables the emergence of a new hybrid practice. Current design practice is invested in the prototyping of these new methodologies. Across the building industry and in research we see a collective push for understanding how this new digital chain can be structured, what are productive exchanges and how a new sense of feedback can lead to smarter design solutions. The InnoChain conference call was answered widely and more than 40 speakers presented the leading examples of this hybrid design practice.

The presentation of innovative projects from practice and research highlighted strategies and tools for interdisciplinary collaboration, advanced design optimisation and material rethinking and led finally to a peer-reviewed publication with UCL Press. **THE BOOK "DESIGN TRANSACTIONS - RETHINKING INFORMATION MODELLING FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE"** was published in April 2020 in an OpenAccess model¹.

We finally want to thank all persons and institutions involved in the preparation of these final Innochain events, especially Yuliya Sinke from CITA, who have been instrumental for the organisation and design of the Innochain exhibition and conference.

Editors:
Martin Tamke,
Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen,
Ruxandra-Stefania Chiujdea

¹: <https://www.uclpress.co.uk/products/141560>

01

INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION

**PRACTICE FUTURES:
BUILDING DESIGN FOR A
NEW MATERIAL AGE**

teknologi i arkitektur & design

UDSTILLING: **PRACTICE FUTURES**

BUILDING DESIGN FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE

inochain

The Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts
Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation

31.08
07.12.18

DANNESKJOLD-SAMSØES ALLÉ 51
1451 CPH K · OPENING HOURS: KADK.DK

INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION

PRACTICE FUTURES: BUILDING DESIGN FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE

COPENHAGEN 31. AUGUST - 7. DECEMBER 2018

CURATED BY:

Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen (CITA)
Martin Tamke (CITA)
Yuliya Snke (CITA)
Susan Jøker Johnsen (KADK)

INTRO

The Innochain exhibition **PRACTICE FUTURES: BUILDING DESIGN FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE** at KADK in Copenhagen showcased the results of the 15 Innochain ESR projects from the 6 institutions. The exhibition showed the individual results of the ESR projects and their relation to the involved 14 cutting edge industry partners from across the interdisciplinary field.

The exhibition showcased the investigation of Innochain into the extended digital chain in its full breadth – the way that a shared digital platform can allow tools for analysis, fabrication and material design to interface so as to create new interdisciplinary methods and digital workflows for future building industry. The breadth of the inquiry was shown through a mix of physical prototypes, demonstrators and digital tools, presenting: how digital tools can make a new use of traditional craft techniques, how resource aware optimisation can lead to new structural designs and how shared digital platforms can lead to a new understanding of collaboration.

is
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**ADAPTIVE
ROBOTIC-
CARVING**
GIULIO
BRIGNARO
LONDON METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
SOPHIE SPINNAKEN
CHRISTOPHER WILSON
/ B&P - BLANKENHORN GROUP

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**APPLIED
ROBOTICS,
CONTROLLED
MATERIAL DEPOSITION**
ARTHUR
PRIOR
LONDON METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
FOSTER + PARTNERS

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**DESIGN
ASSEMBLY
LIFE**
LONDON METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
FOSTER + PARTNERS

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**MILD
SHELL-
PRINTING
HANS
HUTTEL,
LONDON METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
FOSTER + PARTNERS**

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**CONCRETE
ON FOOTING**
LONDON METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
FOSTER + PARTNERS

is
08
**CONCRETE
ON FOOTING**
LONDON METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
FOSTER + PARTNERS

VIEW OF THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION WITH THE CENTRAL LOUNGE UNDER THE GRIDSHELL INSTALLATION BY EFILENA BASETA (ESR07)

WHY AN EXHIBITION

Innochain shares an experimental research-by-design methodology focussing on design-led physical experimentation and full scale prototyping. A series of three exhibitions provides a mean to showcase and review these physical experiments alongside other scientific results and dissemination activities within the ESR project. The exhibition creates opportunities for exchange and speculate within with the network and with individuals and organisations outside Innochain.

The research exhibitions are curated by an experienced exhibition team established by the Innochain leaders from the respective exhibition venues. The curatorship provides a mean to guarantee a high quality communication of each project to the breadth of the expected visitors from the general public to scientific audience

LEFT: A RANGE OF MEDIAS ARE USED TO DISSEMINATE SCIENTIFIC CONTENT (VASILY SITNIKOV - ESR09).

RIGHT: GENERAL AND SPECIFIC INFORMATION ON EACH ESR PROJECT IS PRESENTED ON LARGE BANNERS

A FOCUS ON PHYSICAL EXPERIMENTS

The exhibition provides a mean to highlight and position material research as effective parts of the research enquiry

Scientifically, the physical experiments in Innochain act as material research inquiries by which the concepts and technologies of the research inquiries are evaluated. The method is relevant for design-led research in architecture and engineering as it ties design creativity to research investigation. To employ a research-by-design methodology allows the individual research projects to engage with the solution-led processes of creative trouble-shooting that characterise the design process.

The large exhibition hall at KADK provides sufficient space to showcasing experimental results in forms and sizes from speculative design probes, to material prototypes and full scale architectural demonstrators.

LEFT: LIVE EXPERIMENT ON ICE FORMWORK CASTING OF CONCRETE DURING THE EXHIBITION BY VASILY SITNIKOV (ESR09).

RESULT

The Innochain exhibition had a big impact on several levels:

- It provided a lever for the Innochain projects to focus and produce large scale demonstrators. These acted for many exhibiting ESRs as stepping stones for the next projects after Innochain.
- The curatorship succeeded in developing a concept, which communicates to the general public, without neglecting the scientific density of the projects. This mix attracted finally more than 4.300 unique visitors, many from general public.
- The exhibition produced dissemination material, which was picked up by local as well as international media and was extensively covered in social media.
- The impact of the exhibition as multiplied through further Innochain (p. 151) and local events (p. 183) , which further investigated the relation and position of technology in the field
- Finally the exhibition became a part of the targeted dissemination as well as the everyday of the hosting Institution. This invited and welcomed groups from ministries, association, industry and media, while students and teachers would frequently go to study the exhibition or simply rest in the central lounge like gridshell installation.

LEFT: FULL SCALE PROTOTYPE OF A POTENTIAL ULTRA LIGHT-WEIGHT GFRP FAÇADE BY JAMES SOLLY (ESR 08).

RIGHT: SMALL SCALE 3D PRINT INQUIRING THE STRUCTURAL SETUP OF A PROJECT BY PAUL POINET (ESR 06).

02

THE EXHIBITION - A TOUR

**SHOWCASING RESULTS
OF 15 PROJECTS AND THE
INNOCHAIN NETWORK**

in NETWORK

SNAP

ROCK

BIG

THE IN

South

Architectural and design panels with images and text.

THE NETWORK: INDUSTRY PARTNERS

InnoChain connects “research in practice” with “research in academia” assembling 6 internationally leading academic research environments and 14 cutting edge industry partners from architecture, engineering, design software development and fabrication.

The partnership includes leading actors in contemporary digital design technology. Collectively, we represent a new culture of embedded research in which advanced digital methods is informing design practice, increasing know-how and in turn competitiveness. Together we hold expert knowledge and hands-on experience on advanced digital design methodologies, computational simulation, structural innovation, digital fabrication and material design.

The partnership is strategically structured to include large-scale established industry partners with consolidated design methods and industry leading know-how as well as small scale start-ups cutting edge technologies and experimental design practice. This provides Innochain with a differentiated industrial context and enables the individual research projects to assume varying kinds of technological implementation.

The role of the industrial partners is to co-supervise the PhDs in their individual research projects and host research exchanges inside their industry environments, enabling PhDs to situate and apply their research findings. In Innochain the industry partnership has been instrumental in develop research questions and situating research within an applied setting.

ROK

lego

048975734

**BURO HAPPOLD
ENGINEERING**

structure

BIG

white

**Foster +
Partners**

ROK/RIPPMANN OESTERLE KNAUSS GMBH

Zurich, Switzerland

ROK is a practice for architecture and research.

S-FORM

Deizisau, Germany

The manufacturing of GFRP and CFRP parts for highest mechanic and dynamic demands is the companies focus.

BUROHAPPOLD

21 offices worldwide

BuroHappold Engineering is an independent, international engineering practice that has become synonymous with the delivery of creative, value led building and city solutions for an ever changing world.

STR.UCTURE

Stuttgart, Germany

Str.ucture is an engineering company committed to the development of innovative lightweight solutions.

BIG/BJARKE INGELS GROUP

Copenhagen, Denmark

BIG is a Copenhagen and NewYork based group of architects, designers, builders and thinkers operating within the fields of architecture, urbanism, research and development.

WHITE ARKITEKTER

Stockholm, Sweden

Driven by curiosity, we explore what is possible but seldom imagined. Together, we find sustainable answers, both for today and tomorrow.

FOSTER AND PARTNERS

London, United Kingdom

Foster + Partners understands that the best design comes from a completely integrated approach from conception to completion.

ROBERT MCNEEL AND ASSOCIATES

Barcelona, Spain

Robert McNeel & Associates is a privately-held, employee-owned software development company with sales and support offices and training centers around the world.

DESIGN TO PRODUCTION

Zurich, Switzerland

As pioneers of building information modeling, we close the process chain that links a construction idea to its fabrication.

BLUMER LEHMANN AG

Gossau, Switzerland

We plan and implement innovative timber constructions according to the designs of architects and our own specialists.

FIBR

Stuttgart, Germany

FibR GmbH is a specialist company for computational design and robotic fabrication of bespoke fiber composite structures.

CLOUD 9

Barcelona, Spain

Cloud 9 works at the interface between architecture and art, digital processes and the development of technological materials.

HENN

Berlin, Germany

HENN is an international architecture office with 65 years of expertise in the fields of culture and office buildings, teaching and research as well as development, production and masterplanning.

SMITH INNOVATION

Copenhagen, Denmark

Smith Innovation is an external R&D agency for private and public companies and organisations working within the built environment and its related industries.

PROJECT:

INTEGRATED MATERIAL PRACTICE IN FREE-FORM TIMBER STRUCTURES

TOM SVILANS (ESR02)
COPENHAGEN, DENMARK

CITA - CENTRE FOR
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
AND ARCHITECTURE

BLUMER LEHMANN AG
/ WHITE ARKITEKTER

Wood has gained a new relevance in contemporary construction because it is sustainable, renewable and stores carbon emissions. This project examines the design and fabrication of large-scale free-form timber structures. By proposing an integrated material practice in which design intent is informed by material and fabrication constraints, the project aims to discover new potentials in timber architecture.

The project creates new ways of augmenting existing design modelling tools with lightweight material- and fabrication-specific information. By integrating 3D scanning as a key component in the design-to-manufacture process, it uses sensing as an integrated tool for material calibration in the fabrication process.

The project primarily affects the way architects and designers can interface with material and fabrication constraints of engineered timber, and challenges existing industrial workflows by proposing a reshuffling of the fabrication process and the integration of digital feedback systems. By suggesting new means by which timber architecture can be built, it also presents new perspectives in what timber architecture can be; how it can be shaped and what spaces it can engender.

CONTEXT

Timber is one of the oldest building materials in the world. Its huge material diversity and breadth of application have made it a key material in the development of modern civilization. The use of wood in architecture and construction has led to long building traditions throughout history and a wealth of knowledge about - and innovation into - its behaviours and properties.

Technological developments today have changed the way in which we observe, sample, and interact with the world around us.

NEW GLULAM TYPES EXPLORE NOVEL FABRICATION STRATEGIES FOR GLUELAMS AND POINT TOWARDS NEW FORMS OF TIMBER STRUCTURES.

Digital sensing tools - 3d scanning, digital optics, smart systems - have enabled us to acquire more and more data from the real world, and to use it as inputs into vast computational models and simulations. This new way of looking at the world allows us to reconsider timber in a new light.

AUGMENTED WOOD

The development of manufacturing techniques and structural adhesives in the early 20th century led to the introduction of glue-laminated timber. This highly controlled and industrialized wood makes it possible to surpass the limits of scale set by individual logs and to improve the structural performance of the resultant structural members by eliminating defects and homogenizing the properties of the constituent wood. While this has led to new and dramatically different timber architectures, a closer and critical look at established timber fabrication processes and the capabilities of digital sensing and information modelling today point to new avenues of exploration.

MATERIALLY-INFORMED MODELLING TOOLS FOR FREE-FORM
TIMBER STRUCTURES.

INTEGRATED PRACTICE

This research project proposes that the integration of digital sensing into material- and fabrication-aware modelling tools can lead to new workflows in the design and manufacture of free-form timber structures. It proposes three different notions of feedback between design, process, and fabrication that together define a new practice centered around glue-laminated timber. This is investigated through a practice-based-research methodology as a set of experiments and prototypes.

Direct feedback using digital sensing tools connects the material reality during the fabrication process with the digital information model of the whole project. An industry secondment at Blumer Lehmann explored different types of direct feedback and ways of integrating digital sensing into an active production of a large-scale free-form timber project.

Process feedback reconsiders established sequences of operations in timber production and explores how setting up new and iterative links between these operations can lead to new types of glulam components. A series of bespoke glulam components was

LEFT: THE INTEGRATING DIGITAL SENSING TOOLS FOR REGISTRATION OF TIMBER IN INDUSTRIAL TIMBER CNC PROCESSES.

RIGHT: CNC MACHINED FREEMFORM TIMBER JOINT

prototyped through workshops with students. Each prototype used a combination of industrial operations in a new way to yield speculative new glulam types that either demonstrated advantages in fabricability or assembly, or pointed towards new forms of timber structures.

Design feedback in the form of simulated material behaviour and fabrication impact embedded into software design tools can enrich early-stage design processes and enable a fluidity between designer and producer. These tools were applied to design proposals which both sought to validate their utility as well as to test how the research could perform in a wider architectural context. A competition proposal for the Tallinn Architecture Biennale 2017 (Grove, Tom Svilans, Paul Poinet) made use of a branching glulam prototype and a detailed glulam model to enable the design and data preparation of hundreds of bespoke elements for an architectural folly. The design of a pedestrian bridge outside of Stockholm - developed during another industry secondment at White arkitekter - took more practical and grounded requirements into consideration while making extensive use of the design modelling tools to explore the formal and structural potential of using free-form glulams. Above all, the project seeks to challenge current timber construction practices and reveal an optimistic future for the use of timber in highly-complex yet materially sustainable architectural projects.

Acknowledgements:

This project is generously supported by industry partners

Blumer Lehmann AG (Kai Strehlke, Martin Antemann) and White arkitekter (Jonas Runberger).

Thanks to the staff and faculty at CITA and the KADK workshops.

Special thanks to the staff and faculty at Aarhus Architecture School for their contribution towards the fabrication of the exhibition piece.

COMPETITION PROPOSAL FOR THE TALLIN
ARCHITECTURE BIENNALE 2017.

PROJECT:

ADAPTIVE ROBOTIC CARVING

GIULIO BRUGNARO (ESR10)
LONDON, UNITED KINGDOM

BSA - THE BARTLETT
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON

ROK - RIPPMMANN
OESTERLE KNAUSS GMBH
/ BIG - BJARKE INGELS GROUP

The research challenges the linear progression from the design intention to its materialisation and focuses on the integration of timber material performances within design to manufacturing workflows. It examines the training of a robotic fabrication system based on a combination of sensing strategies and machine learning techniques.

Today crafting depends on knowledge and material understanding of the craftsman. This project finds ways of formalising this knowledge and embedding it into a steering system. This makes it accessible to all the professions taking part of the design process thereby enabling the exploration of novel design opportunities based on an extended

range of available manufacturing processes and tools.

The proposition uses real-world fabrication data, collected both by human experts and autonomous robotic sessions, to achieve a more accurate geometrical prediction of non-standard tools operations on a specific wood species rather than relying on conventional digital simulation methods unable to deal with non-standard fabrication affordances.

The project seeks to establish a dialogue between different creative human experts and emergent technologies, where the instrumental and material knowledge of a skilled human craftsman is captured, transferred, robotically augmented and finally integrated into an interface that makes this knowledge available to designers.

ROBOTIC CARVING.

TRAINING METHODS

The project develops a series of methods to train a fabrication system for the integration of material performances in timber manufacturing processes, combining robotic fabrication together with different sensing strategies and machine learning techniques, and their further application within a prototypical design to manufacturing workflow.

The research questions the linear progression from the design intention to its materialization within current production practices, as these determine a lack of feedback between the different stages of the process. This forces designers to consider materials as passive receivers of a previously generated ideal form stored in a digital model [1] and reinforces the separation between the act of designing and making [2]. Consequently, design practices can only engage with a limited range of standard manufacturing methods and homogeneous materials. Furthermore, the homogenization of natural material results in heavy industrial processing and material waste.

The goal of the research is to develop a computational framework

LEFT & RIGHT: TRAINING SESSION RECORDED WITH MOTION CAPTURE CAMERAS.

which allows designers to engage with the properties of heterogeneous materials and the affordances of non-standard tools as process drivers, extending the design moment toward the fabrication stage to explore novel design opportunities.

Focusing on subtractive manufacturing with timber and carving tools such as chisels and gouges, the technical core of the research questions whether it is possible to use real-world fabrication data, collected both by human experts and autonomous robotic sessions, to achieve a more accurate geometrical prediction of non-standard tools operations on a specific wood species, and, conversely, if it's possible to reconstruct backwards the robotic toolpath that generated a given carved geometry.

To achieve this, the developed methods present a series of training procedures for a robotic fabrication system where the instrumental and material knowledge of skilled human craftsman is captured, transferred, robotically augmented and finally integrated into an interface that makes this knowledge available to the designer.

The access to robotic fabrication facilities alone, does not improve the well-established workflow of a large design firm. The risk is too use such machines solely as a more articulated version of a common desktop 3d printer: here the shape is defined in a digital model and designers expect to have it materialised a few hours later within a block of a given material.

During the secondment at BIG, the installation within the office spaces of two industrial robotic arms made possible to challenge such understanding through a comparison with conventional milling jobs and introduce their use as design tools - both from a methodological and technological perspective.

Operating within a curatorial approach, the team of designers at BIG has been asked to start the process identifying the set of fabrication affordances, in terms of tools and timber species, within which developing their design.

ROBOTICALLY-CARVED TEXTURE PATTERN.

Following such selection, the robotic fabrication system has been trained accordingly and specifically tuned to operate in such a highly project and material specific domain. Sensor data, collected during a series of recording sessions, has been used to train the system. It is now able to simulate and predict precisely the outcome of the carving operations. Designers at BIG could explore multiple material solutions in terms of patterns and textures marks, before moving to the actual fabrication stage. Such encapsulation of instrumental knowledge into a design interface allowed, not only an effective geometric evaluation, but also provided the designer with an understanding of the outcome generated by specific fabrication parameters and material properties, such as the influence of the grain directionality in the actual carved shape.

Following a similar approach, the collaboration with ROK has benefited from their expertise in manufacturing processes and has been focused on the technical development of the tool and its application in a physical demonstrator as a composite furniture piece for an exhibition display.

The design to manufacturing workflow, conceived as curating process, has been arranged around the selection of the fabrication

FABRICATION STAGE AFTER THE RECORDING AND TRAINING STAGES.

parameters boundaries and considerations about the level of control that designer could operate within those together with the type of feedback to provide through the design interface.

The demonstrator has been used to address challenges such as the balance between top-down decisions and features emerging from timber material agency, using the simulation framework, on one hand, to visualize such unexpected features, and, on the other, to adjust the fabrication parameters to match the initial design intention. While following a similar design logic, each carved board composing the demonstrator, presents individual local features and changes in the pattern arrangements of parallel flutes, due to the control of input design parameters and local features such as grain behaviours and knots.

Both collaborations provided furthermore the opportunity to speculate on the transferability of the methods to another set of materials and tool affordances, where packages of instrumental knowledge are collected within larger libraries and applied to specifically tune different fabrication environments according to the design brief.

To conclude, the research demonstrates, through the support of the industry case studies, the potential of machine learning strategies for the customization of manufacturing strategies. Through the extraction of instrumental knowledge and its integration within a simulation framework made available to designers, these can be flexibly integrated into the workflow of design firms, specifically

References:

[1]: DeLanda, Manuel. 2004. "Material Complexity." In *Digital Tectonics*: 14–21.

[2]: Carpo, Mario. 2011. *The alphabet and the algorithm*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.

"KIZAMU" IS THE DEMONSTRATOR FABRICATED AS PART OF THE ROK SECONDMENT.

PROJECT: **APPLIED ROBOTICS:** **CONTROLLED** **MATERIAL DEPOSITION**

ARTHUR PRIOR (ESR13)
LONDON, UNITED KINGDOM

BSA - THE BARTLETT
SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON

FOSTER + PARTNERS

Prototypes made of 'modelling clay' play a crucial role in car design and are made using a mixture of physical and computer-aided modelling techniques. However, producing clay models is normally a painstaking and complicated activity, which increases time-to-market and the cost of developing new products.

This research has resulted in a unique approach to prototyping that enables modelling clays to be used for Additive Manufacturing. This Liquid Deposition Modelling technology exploits the phase-change properties of modelling clays, allowing complex freeform surfaces to be printed quickly and efficiently – layer by layer.

This reduces the amount of waste, difficult manual labour and time needed to produce prototypes, allowing designers to focus their

effort on creative activities. Overall, this technology promotes the continued role of physical sculpting in automotive design and short-circuits the feedback loop between physical and digital modelling.

BACKGROUND

Automotive design involves a mixed-use of physical and computer-aided modelling techniques, blending craftsmanship and computation to produce the high-quality surfaces the end-user can see and touch. Although for decades the role of clay has been threatened by digital prototyping, today it is widely accepted that physical modelling results in the highest class-A surface quality. However, producing clay models is a complicated and painstaking process.

THE PRODUCTION OF FULL-SIZE VEHICLE PROTOTYPES IS A SEMI-AUTOMATED PROCESS. HALF OF THE WORK INVOLVES MANUALLY APPLYING CLAY TO A STYROFOAM ARMATURE.

THE CHALLENGE

Model production methods are time-consuming, expensive and labour-intensive. The bottleneck is clay application:

- During model preparation, 750-900 litres of heated clay is applied to a Styrofoam armature through entirely manual methods
- This physically demanding and repetitive process takes up to 120 man-hours – employers must balance productivity with OSH compliance (e.g. Assessment of Repetitive Tasks (INDG438), Manual Handling Operations Regulations (OC 313/5) etc.)
- The difficulty of judging the correct thickness of clay to apply typically causes overcompensation, resulting in >15% material waste after models are milled out. Ford is the only automaker known to recycle clay (10% annually)
- Model production hinders time-to-market. Vehicle styling takes a minimum of twelve months before 'design freeze' is reached – for example, designers spent 20,000 man-hours modelling the Ford F-150 Raptor.

Audi's "C3" DESIGN PROCESS COMBINES CLAY, CAD AND CGI

Worldwide, there are 204 automotive design studios with clay modelling facilities. By region, 48% are in Europe, 34% in Asia, 15% in North America and 2% in South America. Studios are particularly concentrated in areas such as Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, California, Coventry, Turin and Shanghai.

These studios consume a lot of clay. Per year:

- Up to 90,700 KG is used at the Ford Product Development Center in Dearborn and up to 80,000 KG at the Mercedes Benz Advanced Design Studio in Sindelfingen
- Collectively, the industry uses 3,000 tonnes, enough to create 2,400 models, which would require 288,000 man-hours for clay loading

In this context, the potential for efficiency gains is significant.

Seeking alternatives, automakers began investing in CGI and VR/AR/MR technologies from the 1990's. Despite major advances, car designers have continued to stick with clay. Life-size models are considered the most direct way of communicating design information.

HYBRID MANUFACTURING: LIQUID DEPOSITION MODELLING (LDM) IS USED IN COMBINATION WITH MILLING.

Automakers are increasingly incorporating additive manufacturing (AM) into design workflows, however, conventional materials (e.g. photopolymers) cannot be reshaped after-the-fact, making design change less direct and spontaneous compared to clay. The use of AM is generally limited to small-scale interior components (e.g. air-conditioning vents, door handles). Modelling clays have not been considered in the context of AM before.

HYBRID MANUFACTURING: MILLING THE PIECE DIRECTLY AFTER LIQUID DEPOSITION MODELLING (LDM)

THE SOLUTION

There are currently no solutions in the marketplace for applying clay automatically. During a three-year research project at University College London, we responded to this need by developing a solution that allows modelling clays to be used for additive manufacturing. This Liquid Deposition Modelling (LDM) technology exploits the phase-change properties of modelling clays, allowing complex freeform surfaces to be printed quickly and efficiently – layer by layer. This offers a pragmatic way for design studios to utilise AM, and maintain the time-proven benefits of clay modelling – a best-of-both-worlds scenario.

This approach:

- Provides a solution for automatically applying clay quickly and accurately
- Makes 'lights-out' (i.e. overnight) production possible – reducing time-to-market
- Provides an obvious way for employers to avoid manual handling operations that involve a risk of injury – Reg.4(1)(a) Manual Handling Operations Regulations (OC 313/5)
- Reduces material waste from >15% to 5%
- Promotes the continued role of physical sculpting in automotive design
- Interfaces with existing downstream workflows and studio equipment (e.g. milling)
- Enables design studios to further extend their engagement with digital manufacturing.

This innovation has so far been demonstrated via a small-scale proof-of-concept machine (TRL 3 – EC definition). The goal is to up-scale this technology, making it suitable for full-size vehicle prototyping in a studio environment.

In collaboration with:

Chavant

DETAIL OF A HYBRID MANUFACTURING PRODUCT DESIGN
PIECE: THE PROTOTYPES ON DISPLAY IN THE EXHIBITION WERE
CREATED THROUGH A COMBINATION OF ADDITIVE AND SUBTRAC-
TIVE METHODS. THE AVERAGE PRINTING TIME WAS 00:10:23
(HH:MM:SS).

DETAIL OF THE INSIDE OF A HYBRID MANUFACTURING PRODUCT DESIGN PIECE USING A 3D FILLING PATTERN

PROJECT:

DESIGN FOR ASSEMBLY

AYOUB LHARCHI (ESR14)
COPENHAGEN, DENMARK

CITA - CENTRE FOR
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
AND ARCHITECTURE

DESIGN-TO-PRODUCTION
/ BLUMER LEHMANN AG

While digital tools support architects, engineers and constructors in almost all aspects of design and manufacturing, the planning and design for the assembly of buildings remains an unexplored area. This project focuses on timber construction and aims to lay the foundations of a novel computational approach for design for assembly.

By combining computer science techniques and design practices from other disciplines, this project defines in a first step a scheme by which professionals can describe, analyse and communicate assembly information.

TOP: COMPLEX TIMBER STRUCTURE WITH BESPOKE JOINTS
ASSEMBLED USING AUGMENTED REALITY DEVICES

PROJECT:

MATERIAL SYSTEM OF CONTROLLED DEFORMATIONS

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BLUMER LEHMANN AG

This project focuses on the development of flexible bending-active structures. Bending active structures make use of a material's inherent behaviours - the ability to bend - to harness structural performance. This behaviour relies exclusively on geometrical constraints, which makes it possible to passively control deformations creating shape-adaptable structures.

Most current kinetic bending-active structures rely on electromechanical actuation which entails energy consumption. Current active bending structures moreover need additional materials (e.g. textiles, cables) in order to become stiffer. This project

investigates the passive actuation of bending-active structures that rely only on material properties and therefore are more sustainable.

In this project, timber is used as a material basis and it shows how flexible joinery systems can be used as reversible blocking points. As the structure bends, it blocks when it meets the timber notch detail. In this way, the detailing of the beams allows the designer to control the deformation of the bending structure. Thus, the design and assembly process become more efficient and deformation is reversible.

INTRODUCTION

The current construction industry has not exploited the full potential of the new technologies that the digital era offers. Thus, construction remains a labour intensive task. Focusing on transportable, temporary structures, such as tents, an efficient construction method is active-bending. This method exploits the elastic bending of thin elements in order to create curved forms.

Nevertheless, the bigger the desired curvature, the smaller the cross-sectional height should be. This results in a lowering of stiffness of the final structure due to the slenderness of its parts. In order to solve this problem, this project researches hybrid active bending structures. In the latter structures, additional elements, such as membranes and cables, are combined with the bending elements in order to stabilize them and increase their stiffness [1]. This technique has been proven possible for up to 30 m span structures.

However, the installation process can become complicated since an equilibrium of forces needs to be achieved [2]. Besides that, the structural calculations of the aforementioned systems can be intricate.

Given the above, the presented research proposes an alternative construction system for temporary structures based on active-bending. The aim is to create an independent relation between the maximum curvature and the stiffness of such structures, relying on digital fabrication techniques. Past research, such as ZipShape, had focused on the materialisation of curved geometries through digitally fabricated constrained systems [3]. However, its assembly and scalability have been proven intricate. In addition, ZipShape aimed for fixed final geometries, rather than transformable ones. On the contrary, the aim of this research is to create a system that facilitates the erection and the reusability of temporary structures.

PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

The proposed system is a multi-layered beam which is flexible when it is flat, and thus susceptible to deformations, and stiff when it is bent on a predefined curvature. The flexibility relies on the relative slip between the layers, while the final increased stiffness relies on the constraining of the slip. This simple principle has been materialized by introducing gaps between the joinery details of two consecutive layers. By differentiating the gap lengths, the curvature of the final stiff curvature can be controlled. One locking point per beam, where all the layers are fixed, is required in order to facilitate the slip towards the correct direction. From the above becomes apparent that the more the layers of the beam the stiffer the final bent shape becomes. Thus, scalable linear elements can be constructed flat and easily assembled in a curved configuration. By removing the boundary conditions, the element returns to its flat configuration. The reversibility of the elements allows for applications in temporary gridshell structures.

LEFT: PROTOTYPES OF LINEAR ELEMENT WITH ZIG-ZAG JOINT VISUALISE THE PRINCIPLE

RIGHT: INTERACTIVE PROBES ALLOW VISITORS TO EXPERIENCE BENDING WITH FEEDBACK ON FORCES

JOINERY DETAIL

The behaviour and the functionality of the system depend on the joinery detail between the consecutive layers. Two main geometries have been explored: a) the zig-zag and b) the rectangular. The zig-zag detail allows controlled bending in one direction and unconstrained bending in the other direction. On the contrary, the rectangular detail, allows controlled bending in one direction and constrains bending in the other direction. Variations of these two types can lead to structural optimization of the detail, such as rounding corners and increased contact area. Moreover, the distribution pattern of the joinery detail along the element can increase the structural performance, optimising the fabrication time.

MATERIAL

Current research proves that fiber composites, as well as metals, are the most appropriate materials for bending active structures [4].

TIMBER (SPRUCE GL24) BEAMS MILLED BY HUNDEGGER K3

Wood, as a natural fiber composite, has been chosen for this research as a low-cost solution with sufficient structural performance.

Various tests and prototypes, with various cross sections, have been conducted to prove the functionality and scalability of the proposed system. For the fabrication of the aforementioned prototypes, CNC milling with two different machines have been explored: a) a Kuka robot for the small cross sections (15x20 mm), and b) a Hundegger K3 for the larger cross sections (40x60 mm).

FABRICATION

The fabrication with the Kuka robot allows the machining complicated details. For the tests of this research, a milling bit of 6 mm diameter was used to mill laths mounted on a wall. This resulted in filleted corners for the zig-zag specimens where the laths were milled from the sides. However, sharp corners were achieved at the rectangular specimens where the laths were milled from the top. A further limitation for the specific fabrication setup was the maximum length of milling which equals the radius of the robot (approximately 3 m).

ROBOTIC MILLING OF JOINTS IN WOODENE ELEMENTS WITH KUKA ROBOT

It has been noticed that the quality of the milling depends on the cantilevering of the robotic arm.

The fabrication with the Hundegger K3 was challenging and aimed to prove the potential of the mass production of the proposed system. The beams with the zig-zag detail were initially milled from the bottom. Their production process was problematic and resulted in breakages when the beam was cantilevering inside the machine. In order to reduce the vibrations, two beams were milled simultaneously from both sides of one bigger beam. The latter beam was subsequently sliced in two pieces with an electric saw. The incompetence of the K3 to clamp the zig-zag beam resulted in bad finishing and inaccuracies. However, the beams with the rectangular joinery detail were produced smoothly with a good finishing.

GRIDSHELL PROTOTYPES

Two gridshell prototypes, produced with the aforementioned fabrication techniques, have been conducted; one suspended and one cantilevering. Both prototypes have been fabricated from flat

DIFFERENT PROBES INVITED VISITORS IN THE EXHIBITION TO INVESTGATE HANDS ON THE BENDING BEHAVIOR OF LINEAR ELEMENT WITH ZIG-ZAG (LEFT) AND RECTANGULAR JOINERY DETAILS (RIGHT)

elements with equal cross sections and have been shaped into double-curved surfaces by uniform gravitational loads.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the proposed multi-layered beam allows the creation of bending-active structures with controlled stiffness, without limiting the maximum curvature and without the addition of external elements. The behaviour of the system depends exclusively on the geometrical configurations of the joinery details and the material properties. Thus, curved beams can be easily erected from flat elements, since the construction manual is embedded in the joinery details. Two CNC milling process have been used for the digital fabrication of wooden laths and obtained accuracy of the scale of a millimeter. The gridshell prototypes proved the controlled deformation of the double-layered active-bending elements, as well as the scalability of the system. Further steps of the research include

GRIDSHELL PROTOTYPE IN THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION USING CONTROLLED DEFORMATION OF DOUBLE-LAYERED ACTIVE-BENDING ELEMENTS

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INSTALLATION PROCESS OF THE GRIDSHELL PROTOTYPE IN ITS FIRST EXHIBITION IN VIENNA

A SERIES OF ZIG-ZAG BEAMS INVITED THE EXHIBITION AUDIENCE TO TOUCH AND EXPLORE ACTIVE BENDING BEHAVIOUR

PROJECT:

MUD SHELL DRONE SPRAYING

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The Mud Shell project examines new sustainable production methods that can proliferate and develop mud construction. Clay is a natural, cheap and readily available material. However, current building practices avoid this material as it is seen as weak and prone to disintegration. This project investigates how new digital technologies for design and manufacture of mud shells can reintroduce natural materials in the innovative construction market by revisiting some of its most traditional methods such as wattle and daub with robotic spraying and control.

The project uses a drone to spray an erected substructure and has developed a special non-cement based natural mud composite containing only clay sands fibres and natural stabilisers. Through

collaborations with a team engineers and drones experts, the project has created a customised drone control in order to be able to reach and spray evenly the different parts of the buildings and have increased control of the flow and amount of material deposited.

The earthen structure built at KADK highlights the possibility of prefabricating the dry matter modules to be drone sprayed at a later stage. Future users range from dwellers who can be involved in the finishing of his/her own housing system but as well larger companies of construction who could achieve high buildings coatings of natural material enhancing aesthetics and improving inertia without the need of cranes of labour intensive scaffolding buildings.

DEPOSITION PHASING

“Bioshotcrete” is a new technology being developed by a team of robotic experts, architects, engineers, and drones’ specialists, aiming at using drones in the construction industry to spray natural materials over a temporary light formwork until a self-standing shell is completed. This technique consists in projecting paste-like matter composed of clay mixes following precise and customized deposition sequences over a temporary formwork, incorporating computational techniques in the design and fabrication stages, therefore proposing a more sustainable version of shotcrete. In particular, this paper features experiments using drones for spraying wet and dry ranges of clay mixes over a reusable inflatable formwork with the purpose to build monolithic earthen shells. The featured case studies propose specific protocols to control different deposition sequences, describing the proper formulation of clay mixes, the design and production of customized spraying devices, and fitting options in the drone allowing to vary pressure and other drone spraying parameters. The development of Bioshotcrete using robotic fabrication strategies

Permanent construction domaine Du Boisbuchet 2018
Le Nid Du Dragon

could help expand and transform existing construction methods and processes to be applied at large scale, therefore incorporating innovative digital fabrication protocols towards a more sustainable building construction realm.

Spraying concrete on inflatable formwork has a long tradition in shotcrete, a construction method in existence since the 40s, where concrete is pulverized by workers holding a deposition apparatus positioned at different levels of a scaffolding. This technique was developed by Dante Bini with the Bini domes [5], and was widely expanded for different types of constructions, including civil works, buildings, swimming pools, etc. Since its inception, several improvements have been suggested to overcome some of its limitations, such as keeping constant pressure and spraying flow while the concrete mix is applied, and some authors have suggested that considerable improvements can be achieved by incorporating robotic actions to spray the material [6].

An alternative to spraying concrete mix was introduced by Concretecanvas, offering a prefabricated phase of readymade slices of textile and dry concrete that needs to be humidified by spraying

PRODUCTION OF THE INNOCHAIN EARTHEN VEIL: SPRAYING WET EARTH WITH A DRONE IN THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION HALL

water at a later stage. In parallel, a series traditional techniques have been developed over the last years, involving spraying liquid clay mixes over easily mounted very thick lost fromwork of straw balls to generate domes under compression.

The use of temporary formwork has a long history in concrete construction in several modalities, such as fabrics, inflatables, and others. A series of experiments with temporary formwork were developed since 2013, which include self-standing arches

DRY MATTER SEPARATED FROM WET MATTER DRONE SPRAYING IN THE INSTALLATION AT BOISBUCHET

supporting a stretched fabric to provide a shell defining surface serving as temporary support for the robotic spray a variety of clay mixes until the structure reaches a self-standing condition, at which point the temporary formwork is entirely removed [2]. Further experimentations tested the suitability of using inflatable formwork based on advantages such as being recyclable, adjustable, affordable, and easily available off the shelf.

To inquire about the potential of using robotic fabrication in the construction industry based on shotcrete practices and temporary formwork deployment, a number of experiments have been conducted aiming to 3D print using additive fabrication techniques by spraying natural paste-like materials such as clay [3]. This singular technique denominated Bioshotcrete, is based on a precise sequence starting by the material formulation, digital fabrication protocols, and robotic actions, which will be described below with more detail.

LIGHT FORMWORKS

Spraying drones are widely used in several different domains, e.g. agriculture, where various automated solutions have been developed to bring precision and safety to farms and farmers [4].

In such applications, drones usually have to spray certain feature of the environment, e.g., spraying crops with pesticides. In both agricultural and construction robotics, an automated solution includes creating a map of the environment in which spraying drones operate. This may involve piloted flights in order to gather data for further process and create a 3D representation of the environment. This map can be enriched with various knowledge such as density, pressure, only to name a few. Given a map and an objective such as spraying the entire environment (shell), an automotive trajectory generator, called trajectory planner, computes a sequence of poses for an autonomous navigation of drones. The generated trajectory by the planner often must satisfy certain constraints that posed by the applications [1], e.g., temporal constraints on the order of places that have to be sprayed.

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In collaboration with:

DETAIL OF THE MUD VEIL IN THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION

PROJECT:

ICE FORMWORK FOR FORULTRA-HIGH PERFORMANCE CONCRETE

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/ BURO HAPPOLD

Today, concrete is the most common building material, but the process of casting concrete components is complex, expensive and highly resource demanding. This project investigates how to make a sustainable,

zero- waste material system for fabrication of precast concrete components.

Ice Formwork is an ice-based CAM (computer-aided manufacturing) casting mould system that can help to impose complex curvilinear geometry on concrete

using only natural ice. It thereby proposes a entirely waste-free fabrication process. Moreover, this project is examining the automation of numerous operations, such as assembling formwork, placing reinforcement and demoulding. Today these operations require intensive manual labour.

In recent years, much research has been dedicated to the topic of innovation in the field of concrete constructions. The main challenge here is to make more economically viable solutions.

In the case of Ice Formwork, preliminary estimation of production costs is very positive. The reason is it uses well-developed general-purpose technologies in the form of refrigerated cargo containers that so far has laid outside the architectural technologies.

As such, the research engages both parties of architectural production: architects, who gain new freedoms in their choice of design geometry and contractors precast factories benefit from an automated fabrication workflow with very low resource consumption.

A MIX OF MODELS AND SCREENBASED DIAGRAMS EXPLAIN THE PROCESS OF CASTING AND MAKING WITH ICE FORMWORK

A CONCEPT OF LEAN PRODUCTION

Emerged within the development of automotive industry, the concept of lean production nowadays refers to an economic performance of a manufacturing process. This performance is derived through efficient management of material cycles and a high degree of automation.

The concept of Ice Formwork is attempting to bring together these criteria in the industry of precast concrete constructions. In this setup, the use of ice resolves the problem of material waste and manual labour at the stage of formwork dismantling (fig.1) that are big advantages in comparison with conventional casting methods. Additionally, robotic processing of ice for CNC-milling allows automation of formwork production at a relatively low cost. The trade-off is that fabrication environment has to be kept at negative temperatures. However, research around the energy consumption of refrigeration has shown that these expenses won't exceed benefits of the proposed fabrication process as whole.

SAMPLES OF ICE FORMWORK SHOWCASSE THE EFFECT OF MILLING WITH DIFFERENT CNC ROUTERS

ICE CNC-PROCESSING

To cast a particular concrete element using ice formwork, a mould - a negative of the intended geometry - needs to be produced in ice. In this project, the objective is to study digital tools that can be used in ice processing, and to identify the fashion in which ice formwork would meet standards of CAM and automated fabrication. The most popular method of processing ice that has been found in several ice-processing factories is three-axis CNC-milling.

Initial testing has revealed that ice milling is a simple and forgiving process. Since ice is hard and brittle, a carbide single flute straight flat end bit of 6 mm in diameter has been chosen for processing. The tool has performed perfectly when plunging, slot or face milling. Even in tests at the rate of 3 rounds per millimeter (9000 rpm, 3000 mm/min), the resulting geometry was very accurate, without any chipping occurring on the edges even at the milling depth of only 1mm (Fig. 2). The saw dust produced during milling was easy to remove with a soft brush; however a vacuum extraction system would be desirable for larger milling jobs.

SUB-FREEZING CEMENT HYDRATION

The problem of concrete sub-freezing hardening constitutes the core of the current research. The solution that we are proposing has been derived through analytical work in ultra high performance concrete (UHPC) mix designs, development of a special antifreeze admixture, and series of empirical laboratory tests. We've identified that due to a very low water-cement ratio of high-performance concrete, this mix design can be easily adjusted to hardening at negative temperatures. Furthermore, we have found that exposure to the cold on early stages of hardening doesn't cause accountable losses of the total mechanical properties of the resultant cement stone.

SURFACE QUALITY OF CONCRETE CAST IN ICE

Detailed documentation of this work has been previously presented and published in the proceedings of Design Modelling Symposium, Paris 2017 [1], IASS Boston 2018 [2] and the 2nd International Workshop on Durability and Sustainability of Concrete Structures, Moscow 2018 [3].

Speaking of the geometry transfer from ice to concrete, in order to avoid any ice deformations due to thawing at the moment of casting, the initial temperature of fresh concrete had to be identical to that of ice. Departing from this assumption, we've started with developing a chemical composition for an antifreeze admixture that provides self-compacting rheology and facilitates a rapid hydration of cement at temperatures down to -10°C . Furthermore, due to constant low temperature of concrete, the process of cement hydration significantly slows down. In turn, this conditions that the strong exothermal reaction of cement hardening is reduced to a point that the temperature rise is barely noticeable. In result, empirical examination has revealed that our mix design can be cast, set and harden at

negative temperature and doesn't cause any substantial deformations of ice even in direct contact. Prototypes cast in ice illustrate the high quality of the concrete surface finish and prove that no substantial deformations of the ice are occurring in this process (Fig. 3).

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TIMELAPS OF UNMOULDING OF A CASTED CONCRETE PIECE FROM ICE FORMWORK

ICE FORMWORK MADE WITH A 2.5 AXIS CNC-MILLING ROBOT

PROJECT: MULTI-SCALAR MODELLING: SCHEMA-BASED WORKFLOWS AND INTER-SCALAR SEARCH INTERFACES FOR BUILDING DESIGN

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DESIGN-TO-PRODUCTION
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Architecture and the building industry is increasingly based on digital information and communication. New digital design practices allow designers to combine information from site, design, analysis and fabrication to inform design in multiple ways. However, contemporary practices are lacking the tools by which to effectively integrate these data rich environments into existing workflows.

In today's practice, each stakeholder structures and organises their information in proprietary ways. This means that the design space is fractured and difficult to understand as a whole. Where we in everyday culture use search engines to search across different knowledge spaces (the web) these kind of holistic search mechanisms are not available in design.

those processes. This framework is illustrated by practical experiments using schema-based workflows and inter-scalar search interfaces enabling the assembly, visualization and query of the produced data. Within the realm of highly complex and large-scale architectural projects, quitting the tender phase does not necessarily implicate that all digital objects have been actually “frozen”, meaning that the geometry is fully generated and accessible. Those will be further design-processed during the post-tender phase, once the materials used and available machines are perfectly known and the fabricator actually needs specific data (before and during construction). This data is generally very expensive, since it takes time to generate, organize and share amongst all trades.

DESIGN-TO-PRODUCTION

The consultancy practice Design-to-Production organises its objects through specific layer tables within Rhino3d, enabling both its storage and classification. Similar to a directory tree structure, a layer table is organised into different levels (or depths) that

REPRESENTING INFORMATION: FROM THE TRADITIONAL LAYER TABLE TO THE SUNBURST DIAGRAM.

communicate from a root layer to all its successor sub-layers.

Generally, both the root-layer (containing the component's label) and the leaf-layers (containing its geometries) are defined through the protocol generating the information. The intermediate layer levels are identified by the component's name and mainly serve to structure the information in order to make it more human-readable, defined by the expert user him/her-self. Therefore, the layer tree is independent from the "semantics" of the component and just a UI-feature.

Depending on the nature of the component (being a beam, an opening, a facade element, etc.), it will be stored within a specific submodel (or worksession) that refers to a larger master file from which data communication with other submodels becomes possible (Scheurer, 2012).

In order to get a better understanding of Design-to-Production's data structure, the layer table has been extracted and displayed through the form of a Sun-burst Diagram (Fig. 1). Each level is represented by a circle, the latter being divided into smaller arcs corresponding to the sibling layers, the offset of each arc corresponding to the number of objects contained within each layer.

Such diagram allows the user to obtain a better insight into the general structure and intricacy of the layer table, and quickly spotlight the specific layers that contain a high number of objects.

LAYER STALKER

The functionality of the corresponding Sunburst Diagrams (acting so far as pure data visualization tools) has been extended by introducing interaction features through "LayerStalker" (Fig. 2), a developed imbedded interface within Rhino3d from which the user is able to call multiple layers based on generic strings or keywords (e.g. "detailed volume", "dowel", "drill", "axis", "connector", etc.).

This is exemplified in Fig.2, where the value "drill" is called, displaying all objects whose respective layer names contain the exact same tag, and hiding all the others.

The multi-scalar model on the right displays the selected layers and

highlights the gathered centralized informatio within the Rhino3d viewport, on the left.

LAYER EXPLORER

Because the layer hierarchy might be too intricate and complex to be grasped and comprehended as a whole, my research suggests that a zoomable interface would be required, letting the user navigate between the dif-ferent levels of resolution that he or she defined up-stream. "LayerExplorer" (Fig. 3) has been developed and built within the Processing environment platform, based on an existing sketch and adapted for this specific scenario. It takes as input the existing Rhino3d's LayerTable data structure and translates it within the Processing's interactive environment.

SCHEMA BUILDER

The next experiment is built on top of Speckle, a main data communication protocol platform developed by ESR Dimitrie

ONE OF THE TERMINAL OSLO PAVILIONS MODELLED BY DESIGN-TO-PRODUCTION AND ITS RESPECTIVE INTERACTIVE LAYER TABLE REPRE-SENTED AS A SUNBURST DIAGRAM. HERE, THE VALUE "DRILL" IS CALLED, DISPLAYING ALL OBJECTS WHOSE RESPECTIVE LAYER NAMES CONTAIN THE EXACT SAME TAG.

Stefanescu. Speckle offers at its core a database generic enough to host geometrical objects coming from various software platforms. The minimum amount of information necessary for the future reconstruction of those objects is stored along with customized user dictionaries containing parallel information defined by the user. This enables the construction of custom schemas embodying a neat hierarchy of objects and subobjects, allowing external stakeholders to operate meaningful queries from the database at later stages. Based on those observations, a generic UI/UX interface, called “SchemaBuilder” (Fig. 4), has been developed, allowing to seamlessly build custom nested hierarchies of geometries, ready to be sent to the Speckle’s database (along with their respective schemas and properties/attributes). It would prove to be extremely useful for the many consultancy practices that interact with data rich models at late stages in the design process.

SCHEMABUILDER'S CURRENT USER-INTERFACE

LAYEREXPLORER, A PROTOTYPE INTERFACE ALLOWING THE USER TO NAVIGATE

BETWEEN THE DIFFERENT HIERARCHICAL LEVELS FROM THE RHINO3D'S LAYER TABLE.

3D PRINTED MODELS VISUALISE THE DATA BASED RESEARCH
PROBES IN THE ESR 06 PROJECT

PROJECT:

CONCRETE DEPOSITION

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WHITE ARKITEKTER

This project investigates concrete tectonics in large-scale additive manufacturing (3D printing). The process of placing concrete by deposition signifies a fundamental departure from current casting techniques. The formation of concrete-flow is no longer determined by the restraint and control provided by a static mould, but by the plastic behaviour of the material itself coupled with the programmable path of the deposition nozzle.

In extrusion-based additive manufacturing, a digital model is typically materialised through the build-up of lines in a stratified layering of material in which the notion of 'resolution' is used as a measure of the level of detailed precision. However, when the process of deposition is scaled-up to building production, resolution increasingly becomes a trade-off between the height of each layer and time.

While in conventional additive manufacturing workflow the manufacturing toolpath is generated in a separate process after the completion of a design, this project pursues an alternative approach where the line itself is treated as an architectural element in the design process. Through the controlled interweaving of lines the project explores additive tectonics in relation to architectural qualities and concrete performance.

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ESR 11: 3D PRINTS VISUALISE THE RESEARCH TRAEJCTORY AND DESIGN SPACE OF THE PROJECT.

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ALTERNATE MEANS OF DIGITAL DESIGN COMMUNICATION

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The current proliferation of different design platforms make it difficult to share information amongst stakeholders in the building industry, where information is fragmented and redwired creating out of sync data in design teams.

This project "Speckle" creates a shared platform through which different stakeholders can communicate and share information as you design, development and thereby save the time for many in the design process. The aim is to create an open digital architecture framework for designing, making, and managing the built environment and specifically, track the design associated with communication in the digital design process by increasing data transparency and information mobility. An approach to connect everyone in a system and Ai, Speckle puts the social and informal aspects of design communication first, and aims to increase human intelligence rather than replace it.

The year-long community that has emerged around Speckle is growing exponentially, both in terms of opportunities as well as challenges. As a result of the success of the research project, it has been used by other universities to help explore the relationship between other universities and companies than AEC industry are starting to engage.

PROJECT:

ALTERNATE MEANS OF DIGITAL DESIGN COMMUNICATION

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The current proliferation of different design platforms make it difficult to share information runningly within the building industry, where information is translated and redrawn creating cut off points in the design chain.

This project “Speckle” creates a shared platform through which different stakeholders can communicate and share information across design development and thereby paves the way for a more inclusive design process. The aim is to create an open digital infrastructure framework for designing, making, and operating the built environment and specifically tackle the friction associated with communication in the digital design process by increasing data transparency and information velocity. As opposed to current

endeavours in automation and AI, Speckle puts the social and informal aspects of design communication first, and aims to enrich human intelligence rather than replace it.

The 300+ strong community that has emerged around Speckle is growing continuously, both in terms of supporters as well as actual contributors. During the course of the research project, it has been used by other universities to enable new research, and leading international companies from the AEC industry are starting to engage.

**Speckle is open
digital infrastructure
for designing, making
and operating the
built environment.**

The main goal of this research project is to analyse how complex simulation based design can be collated and communicated internally, within a design team, as well as externally, with the various stakeholders involved in the design process.

Communication is an essential activity that permeates the design industry in all its aspects, from ideation to materialisation - from the drawing board to the shop floor. The contemporary context involves a growing number of stakeholders from various backgrounds that. They enable through their interaction the definition and subsequent solving of design problems at various scales, thus ultimately leading to the production of the built environment. Current digital

methodologies (BIM) are primarily reliant on technical models of communication. These are through their direct imposition on the essentially social phenomenon of designing, detrimental to the process they are trying to enable.

Current digital infrastructure for design locks users furthermore in proprietary solutions for data sharing, which is neither truly open nor does it allow to build on top.

Therefore, this is what we've set up to build, from the internet up: a truly open, vendor-neutral platform that connects Architecture, Engineering and Construction in an ethical data rich environment.

github.com/speckleworks

Contributors:

Dimitrie Stefanescu, UCL

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Jon Mirtschin, GeometryGym

& others.

PROJECT:

MULTIPLE STATES OF EQUILIBRIUM FOR BENDING-ACTIVE TENSILE STRUCTURES

EVY L.M. SLABBINCK (ESR01)
STUTTGART, GERMANY

ITKE - INSTITUTE OF
BUILDING STRUCTURES AND
STRUCTURAL DESIGN

FOSTER + PARTNERS
/ MC NEEL EUROPE

Bending-active tensile structures are material efficient and lightweight architectural solutions that have their roots in ancient tent structures. A combination of bending-active elements together with a membrane introduces new integrative solutions into the design space of adaptive structures, by using their potential for having multiple states of equilibrium.

Currently the implementation and construction of these kinds of structures is limited by the complexity of design and analysis as well as their fabrication. By exploring scale, stability, adaptivity, application, component customisation and design to fabrication processes, this project finds new workflows that take design, construction and material constraints into account and explores the design space for possible systems and their implementation into architecture.

INTRODUCTION

Bending-active tensile structures are material efficient and lightweight architectural solutions that have their roots in ancient tent structures. A combination of bending-active elements together with a membrane introduces new integrative solutions into the design space of adaptive structures, by using their potential for having multiple states of equilibrium. The current problems with hybrid bending-active tensile structures, i.e. the complex modelling, analysis, fabrication, construction and detailing, restricts these structures from being built in a larger scale and they have so far been strictly built in a research and educational environment. The obvious goal of changing the shape of hybrid bending-active tensile structures challenges the reciprocal equilibrium between both structural elements.

The aims are to propose an integrated workflow from design to construction and to explore the design space for possible systems and their implementation into architecture. These structures can be programmed to adapt to and modify environmental or occupant behaviour via embedded sensors, by responding to

PROBES OF BENDING ACTIVE TEXTILE PLATE HYBRIDS IN THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION

stimuli such as light or noise levels, temperature, proximity, or preference. The research aims to investigate into depth the scale, stability, adaptivity, architectural applications, component customisation and design to fabrication processes with several demonstrators / experiments, i.e. BAT 01, ICD / ITKE Research Pavilion 2017-18, Computational Bamboo demonstrator (IAAC GSS Quito 2018), and BAT 02.

COMPUTATIONAL BAMBOO (IAAC GSS)

The computational bamboo installation was built in July 2018 as part of the IAAC Global Summer School in Quito, Ecuador. The structure is constructed from bending-active bamboo laths and rods and will be showcased for 3 months at the Museum of Interactive Science in Quito, Ecuador. The workshop, which resulted in a large demonstrator (Fig. 01), combined natural local traditional building materials with new computational methods for design combined with traditional fabrication.

The workshop aims to have an impact on different levels. First, the installation combines traditional materials with cutting-edge computational technology. It teaches local students to use computational design and the resulting demonstrator showcases the advantages of computational design in Quito. Second, the pavilion uses exclusively natural materials: bamboo rods and laths for the structural system, and jute cord for the joint details. In keeping with the sustainable materials, the bending-active system is very materially- efficient as well. There is no need for complex formwork nor moulds, nor high end machinery. Finally, computation is opening new ways for interacting with our structures. Within this context, current architectural paradigms are shifting from designing static building models to the design of more dynamic and behavioural ones. Structures can now be designed to physically respond to stimulus coming from dynamic and unpredictable environments for improving design criteria performances. However, the problem of designing such structures relies on the unpredictability of its

geometrical shape. Contrary to standard design processes where shape can be defined in advance, the final geometrical configuration of these flexible structures relies on the integration of material behaviour as the main agent driving the entire formation process. The workshop explored non-standard dynamic articulations of bending-active elements by bridging the gap between physical and digital models with an in-house made software: Elastic Space.

BAT 02

The BAT 02 is an adaptive integrated hybrid meeting room, in collaboration with Seiichi Suzuki, industry partner Foster + Partners and Tesler + Mendelovitch.

The obvious goal of changing the shape of hybrid bending-active tensile structures challenges the reciprocal equilibrium between both structural elements (the bending-active elements and the membrane).

On the one hand, a high strain flexible fabric (e.g.

Lycra) is restrained in scale under external loading, on the other hand a low strain structural fabric (e.g. glass-fibre PTFE) needs a cutting pattern to generate a doubly curved geometry and has a limited amount of moving allowance without wrinkling. There is need for a new approach to let these hybrid modules move. An integration of different structural elements and materials are proposed for aesthetic, acoustic and structural advantage, which allow the structural system to be programmed for specific zones: pure tensile, locked compressive zones, transition from tensile to compressive and bending and simple folding.

The structure steps away of a clear boundary between a pure textile supported by bending-active rods, but creates a true hybrid on structural and material level.

ICD ITKE RESEARCH PAVILION 2017-2018

The pavilion is an adaptive plate bending-active hybrid structure, part of the annual pavilion series produced under the leadership of Prof.

Knippers (itke) and Prof. Menges (ICD). The novel adaptive structural typology is based on the reciprocal equilibrium of CFRP bending-active plates and a GFRP-PTFE membrane. The structure pushes the boundaries in computational design and analysis, scale, material and adaptive technology.

Acknowledgements:

BAT 02: with the support of Seiichi Suzuki, Foster + Partners, Tesler + Mendelovitch and Cut & Construct London

Computational Bamboo (IAAC GSS Quito 2018): in collaboration with Seiichi Suzuki, IAAC, PUCE, and MIC

ICD/itke Research Pavilion 2017-18: ITKE (J. Knippers, A. Mader, E. Slabbinck, S. Suzuki) ICD (A. Menges, O. Bucklin, L. Vasey), in collaboration with ITFT, ITECH master studio, IIGS

RENDER BAT 02

PROJECT:

INTERACTIVE MULTIPLE CRITERIA SEARCH IN EARLY DESIGN PHASE

ZEYNEP AKSÖZ (ESR04)
VIENNA, AUSTRIA

UNIVERSITY OF
APPLIED ARTS VIENNA
INSTITUTE OF ARCHITECTURE

FOSTER + PARTNERS
/ MC NEEL EUROPE

The making of a building usually follows a linear process starting with the early design draft, to engineering analysis – to optimisation. This process, though, is time consuming and costly - and based on inconsistent digital systems.

This project examines how architects and designers can use data harvested from all stages in the process in the early design phase to negotiate between performative design objectives and aesthetic aims, and how this awareness can positively influence optimisation procedures in later design stages. By integrating generative processes at the very beginning of the design it provides an interactive environment that give designers the possibility to develop their

designs while evaluating and improving them in real time.

The digital tools developed within the projects framework motivate professionals to define and evaluate design goals from the early phases.

As a result, a multi-disciplinary dialog emerges between professionals and stakeholders to understand the nature of the design problem early on.

LARGE SCALE 3D PRINT OF A HYPER OPTIMISED LATTICE BEAM
USING MACHINE LEARNING

INSIDE VIEW OF 3D PRINT OF A HYPER OPTIMISED LATTICE BEAM
USING MACHINE LEARNING

PROJECT:

VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING OF FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMERS

JAMES SOLLY (ESR08)
STUTTGART, GERMANY

ITKE - INSTITUTE OF
BUILDING STRUCTURES AND
STRUCTURAL DESIGN

FOSTER + PARTNERS
/ FIBR

As people build higher to provide greater urban density, use increasingly remote sites and try to reduce material consumption, additive-manufacturing processes for high-strength/low-weight materials offer exciting possibilities. While extrusion-based “3d printing” methods are limited in deposition rate, as material solidification is required during fabrication, Coreless Filament Winding (CFW) provides a high-speed alternative through the sequential laying of uncured fibre bundles followed by a secondary curing phase.

This project presents a digital design toolset that has the embedded manufacturing awareness needed to create building components with CFW. Through these examples it explores the wider need for virtual prototyping tools to support designers who wish to engage with

customisable and directional material. Tools created through this project were developed in a collaborative research environment and attempt to enable greater depth of discussion between designer, engineer and fabricator at an earlier project stage.

RESEARCH BY FABRICATION

The research consists of three major components: Learning the (already-well-developed) fabrication process of coreless filament winding, involvement with live projects to provide relevant situational input and the development of useful digital design methods that can be deployed on future construction projects that utilise CFW.

Engagement with physical projects has therefore been the crux around which the research has developed through the three years, with these case-studies providing fabrication knowledge, new examples of possible uses for CFW in construction and input to the development of digital design tools.

MATERIAL DISTRIBUTION IN AN ELEMENT OF THE ELYTRA FILAMENT PAVILION

The process of construction is a collaborative one. Through the research, four collaborative projects have been realised and elements of these are represented in this exhibition. In all cases further detail may be found at www.innochain.net/esr8-virtual-prototyping-frp/

ELYTRA FILAMENT PAVILION

The Elytra Filament Pavilion is a 200m² canopy, assembled from 41 coreless-wound components with a structural mass of only 9kg/m². This first project provided significant knowledge on Coreless Filament Winding from experienced researchers and gave opportunity for initial studies into the digital optimisation of fibrous structures. A photograph of the completed structure and a test component created during project development are presented here. The exhibited component is identical in form and scale to those installed in the pavilion. It weighs approximately 30kg and is designed to carry a cladding panel plus the wind and snow loads expected on a protective canopy.

FULL SCALE GFRP ELEMENT FROM THE ELYTRA FILAMENT PAVILION IN THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION

RESEARCH PAVILION 2016-2017

The ICD/ITKE Research Pavilion 2016/2017 is a 12m long cantilevering structure fabricated as a single part by coreless filament winding performed in collaboration between two industrial robots and a Drone (UAV). The project provided opportunities to test early strategies for fibre winding simulations and to develop further structural optimisation techniques. A photograph of the completed structure is presented here.

OPTIMISED FIBRE BEAM PROTOTYPE

Inspired by ongoing research in the Specialist Modelling Group (SMG) at Foster+Partners on the digital fabrication of optimised structural components, this prototype emerged from asking how a coreless-wound optimised beam would look. While extrusion-based 3d printing methods can slowly place material at any location in space, coreless winding quickly places linear tows of material that must span between boundaries.

This prototype presents a first experiment in finding balance between optimum material placement and this key fabrication constraint.

STRUCTURAL MODEL, RP16/17 (c) ICD/ITKE

FIBRE FACADE SYSTEM PROTOTYPE

The prototype facade system exhibited here demonstrates how the coreless winding system can be used to enable geometric freedom in a typical building element and shows how little composite material is required to support typical loads.

The winding scaffold consists of simple adjustable-length poles fixed to a metal base. Fibres wound around this minimal form can easily create a unique panel orientation while adhering to limited possible fixing points on the building.

The resulting components weigh between 300g and 1kg and are designed to support glass panes (polycarbonate is used here) plus the expected wind loads.

TOP TO BOTTOM: CONTINUOUS TOPOLOGY OPTIMISATION RESULT, PROPOSED FIBRE LAYOUT FOR OPTIMISED BEAM, FABRICATED BEAM, AS EXHIBITED IN THE EXHIBITION

WINDING FRAME FOR FACADE SUPPORT COMPONENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

Elytra Filament Pavilion:

Design, Engineering and Fabrication Team:

Achim Menges with Moritz Doerstelmann, ICD - Institute for Computational Design and Construction. Team included Marshall Prado, Aikaterini Papadimitriou, Niccolo Dambrosio, Roberto Naboni, with support by Dylan Wood & Daniel Reist

Jan Knippers, ITKE - Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design. Team included Valentin Koslowski & James Solly (structural development), Thiemo Fildhuth (structural sensors) Thomas Auer, Transsolar Climate Engineering/Building Technology and Climate Responsive Design, TU Munich. Team included Elmira Reisi & Boris Plotnikov

Commissioned By:

Victoria & Albert Museum, London 2016

Supported By:

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Research Pavilion 2016-2017:

Project Leads:

Professor Achim Menges, Institute for Computational Design and Construction, Professor Jan Knippers, Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design.

Scientific Development: Benjamin Felbrich, Nikolas Früh, Marshall Prado, Daniel Reist, Sam Saffarian, James Solly, Lauren Vasey

System Design, Development, Fabrication and Construction (ITECH Class of 2017): Miguel Aflalo, Bahar Al Bahar, Lotte Aldinger, Chris Arias, Léonard Balas, Jingcheng Chen, Federico Forestiero, Dominga Garufi, Pedro Giachini, Kyriaki Goti, Sachin Gupta, Olga Kalina, Shir Katz, Bruno Knychalla, Shamil Lallani, Patricio Lara, Ayoub Lharchi, Dongyuan Liu, Yencheng Lu, Georgia Margariti, Alexandre Mballa, Behrooz Tahanzadeh, Hans Jakob Wagner, Benedikt Wannemacher, Nikolaos Xenos, Andre Zolnerkevic, Paula Baptista, Kevin Croneigh, Tatsunori Shibuya, Nicolás Tempereri, Manon Uhlen, Li Wenhan.

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Department of Evolutionary Biology of Invertebrates, Univ. Tuebingen – Prof. Oliver Betz

Department of Palaeontology of Invertebrates, Univ. Tuebingen – Prof. James Nebelsick

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Optimised Fibre Beam Prototype:

Thanks to Moritz, Leo and Andre from FibR for the many hours they put into producing this piece.

Fibre Facade System Prototype:

Thanks to Moritz and Teo from FibR for their input to the overall design and fabrication details for the installation.

Supported by:

facade fixing sponsor

Pauli + Sohn

THREE FIBRE WOUND DEMONSTRATORS OF ESR08 (BEAM, ELEMENT, FAÇADE) IN THE INNOCHAIN EXHIBITION

PROJECT:

INTEGRATING BUILDING PHYSICS FOR PERFORMANCE CONTROL

ANGELOS CHRONIS (ESR03)
BARCELONA, SPAIN

IAAC - INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED
ARCHITECTURE OF CATALONIA

FOSTER + PARTNERS
/ MC NEEL EUROPE

As buildings continue to be one of the main contributors of CO₂ emissions that lead to global warming, cooling energy demands are expected to overcome heating energy demands in the coming decades. In order to increase the natural ventilation potential of buildings, advanced cooling strategies are needed.

This project is investigating the potential of wind-driven form finding in architecture, aiming at optimising the natural ventilation potential of buildings. By integrating Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations and shape optimisation methods, it explores how aerodynamic forms can drive the shape of buildings.

In the past years, rigorous efforts for the development of simulation and optimisation tools for buildings have been undertaken. Although in other aspects of sustainable design, such as solar radiation, daylight and energy, these tools have become common ground, CFD simulations that allow designers to evaluate the airflow of buildings are still not integrated.

A number of integration methods for CFD in computational design have been developed and evaluated during this project. Through industrial and academic collaborations, as well as workshops and other dissemination efforts, the project has exposed architects and researchers to CFD simulations and wind-driven form finding while closing the gap between designers and experts.

TOP: MIXED MEDIA PRESENTATION OF ESR03 VIDEO ON 160x80CM PROJECTION BOARD WITH ASSOCIATED CFD OPTIMISED DESIGN PROBES

TOP: 2D CFD SIMULATION (STILL FROM THE EXHIBITION VIDEO)

BOTTOM: DESIGN LINKED 3D CFD SIMULATION (STILL FROM THE EXHIBITION VIDEO)

is
03
INTEGRATING BUILDING PHYSICS FOR PERFORMANCE OF COMPLEX ANGULAR CHROMES
THE INTEGRATION OF BUILDING PHYSICS FOR PERFORMANCE OF COMPLEX ANGULAR CHROMES

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PROJECT: MATERIAL GRADIENT FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMERS: A MATERIAL SOLUTION FOR CLIMATE ADAPTIVE BUILDING ENVELOPES

SAMAN SAFFARIAN (ESR12)
STUTTGART, GERMANY

ITKE - INSTITUTE OF
BUILDING STRUCTURES AND
STRUCTURAL DESIGN

S-FORM / STR.UCTURE

Buildings account for a large portion of global energy consumption and building envelopes as mediators between interior comfort needs and exterior climate conditions, have a huge potential in reducing energy consumption. This project aims to develop a kinetic, lightweight, energy conscious and materially efficient façade shading system that can adjust its shape and configuration in response to atmospheric conditions as well as building occupant preferences.

Flectofold is a compliant mechanism. The façade system is made of set of fibreglass materially graded modules with integrated cushions. As the cushion is inflated, it activates the elastic bending and as a result generates movement and transformation in the façade. In this way, it

intelligently adjust its configuration and controls the penetration rate of solar radiation through the building envelope.

This system provides a number of benefits in comparison to mechanical shading systems. It can harvest the stored elastic energy for movement generation, it has the potential to dramatically reduce mechanical complexity and associated failure rates, it is more resilient to environmental impact and is more suitable for application on complex and free-form architectural surfaces.

CLIMATE ADAPTIVE BUILDING ENVELOPES

This project investigates methods of precise fiber deployment and lay-up patterns for fabrication of Elastic-Kinetic Facade Shading Components. The effects of controlled geometric variations and systematic stiffness differentiations have been carefully studied in a series of prototypes with the aim of achieving higher movement efficiency, optimized cyclic performance and reduced material fatigue.

FLECTOFOLD : TESTING AND PERFORMANCE
MONITORING

PROTOTYPING, MONITORING AND EVALUATION

A series of Flectofold components have been fabricated with incremental and systematic variations in their fiber lay-up pattern and geometric definition. Initial performance tests conducted on Flectofold components, supported the initial hypothesis about the effects of material and geometric change on kinetic performance.

The knowledge acquired via prototyping and data gathered through ongoing performance tests, was utilized in the next phase of the project. This involved up-scaling of the Flectofolds, improving fiber placement, tackling shortcomings of the system in terms of digital control, resolving issues concerning the pneumatic actuation, enhancing the design of supporting elements and integrating all technologies in an architecturally detailed solution.

IMPLEMENTATION AND APPLICATION

In an attempt to contextualize the future application of Flectofold and explore the limitations and possibilities that material gradient FRP shading systems have brought forward, a large scale demonstrator,

FLECTOFOLD : PROTOTYPING AND INCREMENTAL UP-SCALING

consisting of 36 Flectofold components was designed, developed, fabricated and installed as part of „Baubionik – Biologie beflügelt Architektur“ exhibition at the natural history museum in Stuttgart (Germany) in October 2017.

FlectoFold laminates require a small amount of pre-fold in their rest position to prevent snap-through behaviour during actuation. Taking into account that pre-folded Flectofolds, in their abstract geometric form, have an anticlastic shape, and considering the fact that for shading purposes a complete and seamless coverage of underlying surface is necessary, the guiding geometry of the demonstrator surface has been designed in an anticlastic form, which proves to be most suitable considering all geometric and kinematic parameters.

Tessellating the envisioned anticlastic underlying surface into 36 panels, necessitated a substructure design that could accommodate FlectoFold modules of equal size, integrate the pneumatic actuators and secure their correct alignment , include the attachment

FLECTOFOLD DEMONSTRATOR : SUBSTRUCTURE AND SUPPORTING ELEMENTS

“BAUBIONIK - BIOLOGIE BEFLÜGELT ARCHITEKTUR” EXHIBITION, NATURAL HISTORY MUSEUM, STUTTGART, OCTOBER 2017

details for connection to the substructure, incorporate a tilting mechanism to adjust the axial rotation of individual modules for optimal and symmetric surface coverage, and include a pneumatic tubing management system for sake of systematic assembly and maintenance clarity. Shortcomings of the system were addressed in a series of prototypes and the overall design of supporting elements and the substructure was developed into an architecturally detailed solution. This is crucial not only for scientific assessment of the system in research contexts, but also an inevitable step towards future implementation in building and construction industry.

FLECTOFOLD DEMONSTRATOR : SUBSTRUCTURE AND SUPPORTING ELEMENTS

"BAUBIONIK - BIOLOGIE BEFLÜGELT ARCHITEKTUR" EXHIBITION, NATURAL HISTORY MUSEUM, STUTTGART, OCTOBER 2017

In parallel to the design development of the substructure and supporting elements, the design also had to take into consideration the necessary electronic and pneumatic circuits for active and autonomous control of an array of Flectofolds. In order to achieve accurate control over the amount of air-pressure in every single actuator, a proportional pressure control technology from Festo was utilized in conjunction with a number of custom-made electronic circuits. This hardware setup was designed and tested through a series of prototypes during the design development of the demonstrator. Alongside hardware development, an active web-based control user interface was designed, programmed and implemented to work and interact seamlessly with the hardware assembly and provide the possibility to control individual units through mobile and web-based applications.

Apart from showcasing the technology in a public setting, the Flectofold demonstrator has been used to monitor kinetic performance and associated material fatigue in long-term cycles,

FLECTOFOLD DEMONSTRATOR : CONTROL SYSTEM

"BAUBIONIK - BIOLOGIE BEFLÜGELT ARCHITEKTUR" EXHIBITION, NATURAL HISTORY MUSEUM, STUTTGART, OCTOBER 2017

assess application potential on complex and free-form architectural surfaces and analyse suitability as a shading or energy harvesting system.

The collected data and gathered knowledge will inform the next steps in design, development and manufacturing of a range of Elastic Kinetic Structure.

FLECTOFOLD DEMONSTRATOR : CONTROL SYSTEM

“BAUBIONIK - BIOLOGIE BEFLÜGELT ARCHITEKTUR” EXHIBITION, NATURAL HISTORY MUSEUM, STUTTGART, OCTOBER 2017

FLECTOFOLD DEMONSTRATOR, ARRAY OF COMPONENTS, "BAUBIONIK - BIOLOGIE BEFLÜGELT ARCHITEKTUR" EXHIBITION, NATURAL HISTORY MUSEUM, STUTTGART 2017

Credits:

DESIGN DEVELOPMENT

Saman Saffarian

SCIENTIFIC DEVELOPMENT

Larissa Born, Axel Körner, Anja Mader, Renate Sachse, Saman Saffarian, Anna Westermeier, Dr. Simon Poppinga, Dr. Simon Schleicher

WITH SUPPORT OF

Frederik Wulle, Maximilian Nistler, Stefan Abel, Behrooz Tahanzadeh, Dongyuan Liu, Nima Zahiri, Sandie Kate Fenton, Tessa Rudolph, James Solly, Valentin Koslowski

IN COLLABORATION WITH

Fabrication and installation of demonstrators supported by :

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grözing
blechbearbeitung

ISU

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DFG Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft

IBB

BGF

ITFT
FIBER BASED VISIONS

C-CON
UNTERNEHMENSGRUPPE

03

INNOCHAIN CONFERENCE

**EXPANDING INFORMATION
MODELLING - FOR A NEW
MATERIAL AGE**

INNOCHAIN CONFERENCE

EXPANDING INFORMATION MODELLING —FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE

08.10. &
09.10.2018

BLOX | DANISH ARCHITECTURE CENTRE
COPENHAGEN

INNOCHAIN CONFERENCE

EXPANDING INFORMATION MODELLING

- FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE

COPENHAGEN 8.10-9.10.2018

ORGANISED BY:

Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen (CITA)

Martin Tamke (CITA)

Yuliya Slnke (CITA)

Innochain organised the international conference **Expanding information modelling for a new material age** in Copenhagen on 8.-9. November 2018 at the Danish Architecture Centre in the new Blox building by OMA. The conference was organised in collaboration with the Danish BLOXhub organisation and created a forum for transdisciplinary and entrepreneur driven research with more than 200 participants from academia and professional practices and from a wide range of disciplines and countries

THE CHALLENGE

Information modelling challenges the way we think, design and build architecture. By creating a shared digital platform it enables the emergence of a new hybrid practice in which otherwise separate tools and methodologies of design, analysis and fabrication can intersect. Current design practice is invested in the prototyping of these new methodologies. Across the building industry and in research we see a collective push for understanding how this new digital chain can be structured, what are productive exchanges and how a new sense of feedback can lead to smarter design solutions.

What is at stake here is the future of the information model. Expanding simple BIM with more complex requirements to engage and capitalize on analysis, to steer multi objective design spaces and to interface and control fabrication necessitates new kinds of

representations that can handle data rich design enquiries, enable collaboration and manage the complex and cyclical nature of feedback.

THE CONFERENCE

The InnoChain conference presented the leading examples of this hybrid design practice. More than 40 speakers presented innovative projects from practice and research that highlight strategies and tools for interdisciplinary collaboration, advanced design optimisation and material rethinking.

PROJECTS THAT:

- Connect early design thinking with structural and material analysis
- Devise advanced algorithmic approaches to navigate data rich design
- Expand material thinking through novel fabrication processes
- Engage interdisciplinary design innovation

LEFT: BLOX BUILDING

RIGHT: CONFERENCE ROOM IN BLOX

MATRIX OF THE MORE THAN 40 INNOCHAIN CONFERENCE SPEAKERS

KEYNOTES

SESSION FORMAT

The three keynotes highlighted the areas with most pressing need for innovation in the current building practice and highlighted progress in academia and practice in terms of:

- **the future of information modelling as a tool for interdisciplinary collaboration**
- **digital design methods and their impact on rural and urban architecture**
- **the future of interdisciplinary practice**

Innochain introduced a new format for the three keynotes. These have been held in dialogue between two key individuals, representative of the different disciplines and backgrounds involved in all projects of building practice.

The format proved fruitful, as it gave through the different perspectives on the same topic, deep insights into the underlying working of our practice and novel approaches. It also brought partners into conversation, which are due to the current tender processes not in contact with each other - despite being key contributors to the genesis of a builder - as in case of Taro Okabe (architect) and Fabian Scheurer (Fabrication Planning)

KEYNOTE #1:

THE FUTURE OF INFORMATION MODELLING AS A TOOL FOR INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATION

FABIAN SCHEURER is founding partner of designtoproduction and leads the company's office in Zurich. After graduating from the Technical University of Munich with a diploma in computer science and architecture, he worked as assistant for the university's CAAD group, as software developer for CAD-provider Nemetschek, and as new media consultant for Eclat in Zurich.

From 2002 until 2006 he studied the use of artificial-life methods in architectural construction as a member of Ludger Hovestadt's CAAD group at the ETH Zurich and managed to transfer the results to a number of collaborative projects between architects, engineers, and fabrication experts. In 2005 he co-founded designtoproduction as a research group at ETH to explore the connections between digital design and fabrication.

TARO OKABE is a first class registered architect (Japan) and director at Shigeru Ban Architects Europe in Paris who leads European activities of the office. Born in Kawasaki, Japan, grew up in London, Tokyo, Osaka and Paris. After receiving a master degree of architecture at Chiba University, Japan, he started his career as an architect working in several architecture offices, and finally joined Shigeru Ban Architects Tokyo on 2004. Here he was involved in competitions and the realization of projects, such as the Nicolas G. Hayek Centre, Swatch Group HQ (finished in 2007) and the Seikei Information Library (finished in 2006) – both in Tokyo. He was soon involved in international projects, such as the 14th Street Hotel NY, NY, USA (finished in 2008), the Aspen Art Museum, Aspen, Colorado, USA (finished in 2014) and the TDIC Headquarters, Abu Dhabi, UAE (finished in 2010).

KEYNOTE #2:

DIGITAL DESIGN METHODS & THEIR IMPACTS ON RURAL URBAN ARCHITECTURE

ARETI MARKOPOULOU is a Greek architect, researcher and educator working at the intersection between architecture and digital techno-logies. She is the Academic Director at IAAC in Barcelona, where she also leads the Advanced Architecture Group, a multidisciplinary research group exploring how design and science can positively impact and transform the present and future of our built spaces, the way we live and interact. Her research and practice seeks to redefine architecture as a performative “body” beyond traditional notions of static materiality, approximate data, or standardized manufacturing. Areti is founder and principal of the multi-disciplinary practice Design Dynamics Studio, and co-editor of Urban Next, a global network focused on rethinking architecture through the contemporary urban milieu.

PHILIP YUAN Professor, PhD Advisor of CAUP, Tongji University; Guest Professor, MIT; Council Member of Architects Sector, Architectural Society of China; Council Member of Digital Fabrication Sector, Architectural Society of China; Director of Academic Committee of Shanghai Digital Fabrication Engineering Technology Center.

Philip Yuan focuses on the research of Digital Design and Intelligent Construction. He has been awarded a variety of prizes including the 2014 Wienerberger Brick Award, 2015 Shenzhen Biennale Popularity Award and 2016 Gold and Silver Prize of Architectural Design, etc. Philip F. Yuan has published more than 170 theses on academic architectural journals and magazines and 10 books including Collaborative Laboratory, From Diagrammatic Thinking to Digital Fabrication, Digital Fabrication and Computational Design.

KEYNOTE #3:

THE FUTURE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY PRACTICE

HANIF KARA is Design Director – AKT II, Professor in Practice – Harvard GSD Professor Hanif Kara is a design director, educator and co-founder of London-based structural engineering firm AKT II. Under his leadership, the practice has gained an international standing in the field of the built environment, and has won over 350 design awards.

He has been responsible for a number of innovative and pioneering projects but also for raising the profile of ‘design’ both in the construction industry and the wider community. His particular ‘design-led’ approach and interest in innovative forms, historical structures and material uses, prefabrication, sustainable construction and complex analysis methods, have allowed him to work on unique, award-winning projects with leading designers.

SAMUEL WILKINSON is an associate within Foster + Partners’ Specialist Modelling Group (SMG), the architecture practice’s multi-disciplinary research and development group. Since 2014, he has worked on various research projects in collaboration with universities or other companies, such as developing large-scale 3D printing with concrete, plastic, and metal, drone mapping for construction sites, and NASA’s Mars habitat challenge.

He studied architecture and environmental design at the University of Nottingham in 2008, and completed his engineering doctorate at The Bartlett UCL in 2014. He has been involved with Smartgeometry, a non-profit educational organisation for computational design and digital fabrication, since 2011 and a director since 2018.

PAPERSESSION #1: ADVANCED MODELLING STRATEGIES AND NEW WORKFLOW

CHAIR
MARTIN TAMKE (CITA)

This session collects presentations that focus on the analysis, synthesis and communication of data, in design thinking. The presentations discuss how new flows of information can be established and how these integrate with design practice.

CASE #1: MASS ADOPTION OF COMPUTATIONAL ENGINEERING IN PRACTICE: CODE FRAMEWORK, PROJECT ARCHITECTURE & BEHAVIOURS

PRESENTERS: Al Fisher (Buro Happold /London, UK),
Paul Poinet (InnoChain PHD, CITA, KADK /Copenhagen, DK)

Al leads computational development for BuroHappold. Al ensures visual programming, scripting and coding are embedded into engineering teams. Paul focuses in his Doctoral Thesis on Multi-Scalar Modelling techniques for the design of large-scale and free-form architectural projects

CASE #2: ALTERNATE MEANS OF DIGITAL DESIGN COMMUNICATION

PRESENTERS: Dimitrie Stefanescu (InnoChain Phd, The Bartlett, UCL /Speckle)

Dimitrie focuses on creating digital design communication interfaces that enable collaboration between stakeholders in building design.

CASE #3: A GRAPH-BASED PROJECT DATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR CAPTURE & ANALYSIS OF AEC BIG-DATA AND PROJECT TOPOLOGY

PRESENTERS: Mark Pitman (ODS Engineering /Copenhagen, DK)

Mark is the owner of ODS Engineering specialising in development, sales, support and training for software related to simulation and modelling in environmental and sustainable design.

CASE #4: THE VISION OF A DECENTRALIZED, DISTRIBUTED AEC INFORMATION INFRASTRUCTURE USING LINKED BUILDING DATA TECHNOLOGIES

PRESENTERS: Mads Holten Rasmussen (PHD, DTU/Copenhagen,DK)

Mads looks into the methods for solving shortcomings in BIM Building Information Modelling.

PAPERSESSION #2: DESIGN INTEGRATION

CHAIR

METTE RAMSGAARD THOMSON (CITA)

This session focuses on emergence of new hybrid practices in building industry. The shared digital platform allows otherwise separate tools and methodologies of design, analysis and fabrication to intersect. The presentations discuss how this new digital chain can be structured, how collaboration between partners can be productive and how early design thinking with structural and material information can lead to smarter design solutions.

CASE #5: MATERIAL FEEDBACK IN INDUSTRIAL TIMBER PRODUCTION

PRESENTERS: Tom Svilans (InnoChain PHD, CITA, KADK/Copenhagen, DK), Jonas Runeberger (WHITE Architects / Stockholm, SWE)

Tom focuses on the intersection of design, computation and material fabrication. He researches the use of emerging technologies in free-form timber structures.

Jonas explores the relation between digital design techniques, architectural production and experiential effect in both experimental and conventional practice.

CASE #6: INFORMED GEOMETRY: DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATIALLY DRIVEN DESIGN PROCESSES FOR TENSILE STRUCTURES

PRESENTERS: Louis Bergis, (Bollinger + Grohmann Sarl / Paris, FR)

Louis works as an engineer at Bollinger and Grohmann.

CASE #7: PARAMETRIC MODELLING FOR DIGITAL FABRICATION – THREE LARGE SCALE CASE STUDIES

PRESENTERS: Jacob Drachmann (CN3 /Copenhagen, DK)

Jacob is a Civil Engineer based in Copenhagen working with Computational Design and Digital Fabrication methods in construction projects.

PAPERSESSION #3: MATERIAL STRATEGIES

CHAIR
MATHILDE MARENGO (IAAC)

New computer controlled design to fabrication strategies bear a huge potential for more efficient, environmentally safe and sustainable building practices. Their introduction present new relations between man and machine, that radically question established processes. The presentations discuss how new fabrication processes challenge industrial fabrication and how they can be used to rethink building practice while maintaining creative thinking.

CASE #8: DRONE SPARYING ON LIGHT FORMWORK FOR MUD SHELLS

PRESENTERS: Stephanie Chaltiel (InnoChain PHD Fellow, IAAC /Barcelona, ESP)

Stephanie is developing new housing construction systems integrating small robots and more particularly drones.

CASE #9: ROBOTS FOR SKILL DIGITIZATION

PRESENTERS: Johannes Braumann (Robots in Architecture / UFG /Linz, AUT)

Johannes co-founded the Association for Robots with Sigrid Brell-Cokcan in 2011 which acts as a network for creative robot users.

CASE #10: INTEGRATION OF MATERIAL AND FABRICATION AFFORDANCES WITHIN THE WORKFLOWS OF DESIGN FIRMS

PRESENTERS: Giulio Brugnaro (InnoChain PHD, UCL / London, UK)

Guilio focuses on adaptive robotic fabrication processes and sensing methods that allow designers to engage with material behaviours and tool affordances.

PERSPECTIVES /BREAKOUT SESSION

#1

DATA IN DESIGN

CHAIR: Sean Hanna

PRESENTERS: Zeynep Aksoez (IOA), Angelos Chronis (IAAC), Sean Hanna (UCL), Petra Henning (Fojab arkitekter), Henrik Malm (Fojab arkitekter)

Data design is a rapidly developing and highly interdisciplinary field. We will discuss how data modelling can become a more integral part of architectural practice and how it can lead to more informed design. What methods of data analysis are relevant to architecture, how can they be transferred and how do they interface with design creativity.

#2

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING FUTURES

CHAIR: Johannes Baumann (UFG Linz)

PRESENTERS: Zuardin Akbar (Kassel), Nadja Gaudillère (Xtreee), Roberto Naboni (SDU)

Additive manufacturing creates new perspective for the way we build architecture. This panel discusses what material practices are affected and how they are transformed. What are the tectonics of additive manufacture and how do we create new intelligent design to fabrication workflows.

#3

NEW WORKFLOWS

CHAIR: Line Rahbek (Dorte Mandrup)

PRESENTERS: Kåre Poulsgaard (3XN /GXN), Line Rahbek (Dorte Mandrup)

The promise of the digital chain and the ability to integrate early design simulation creates a blurring of the traditional disciplinary borders in the building chain. This panel will discuss the potential of new digital workflows connecting architects, engineers and fabricators. Through best practice examples, we will examine these emergent practices can be organised and how feedback in the design chain is enabled.

#4

PERFORMATIVE MATERIALS AND SYSTEMS

CHAIR: Isak Foged (Aalborg University)

PRESENTERS: Saman Samafarian (ITKE, University of Stuttgart), Isak Foged (Aalborg University), Julian Lienhard (Str.ucture)

Computation allows us to design and manufacture materials with highly specific behaviours. This panel will discuss established and future strategies for digitally informed material fabrication and question how these can intersect with current building practice. What are the methods by which we can engage new performative material understandings and can they eventually lead to a more sustainable building practice.

#5

NEW COLLABORATIONS

CHAIR: Mie Wittenburg (Smith Innovation)

PRESENTERS: James Solly (ITKE, University of Stuttgart) and Moritz Döstelmann (FIBR), Christopher Robeller (TU Kaiserslautern)

The digital chain offers a new platform for rethinking of existing practices in building industry and establish new innovative products and services. We will look at how new partnerships across the disciplines create new ways of building – from new communication platforms and softwares down to building materials and process of fabrication. How can new interdisciplinary and inter-sectoral partnerships innovate the underlying economic models of building industry.

PRE- WORKSHOPS

BLOXHUB
7TH OF NOV 2018 / 13:00 - 16:30
FOLLOWED BY A RECEPTION & NETWORKING

The workshops introduce participants to new tools and practices for the building industry, based on the results of the Innochain project. Each workshop addresses a key challenge in our current architectural, engineering and construction practice. After an introduction to the tools, you will get the opportunity to work with them in a hands-on manner. In order to discuss how to integrate the Innochain developments in your current and future practices, we encourage you to bring your own laptop and projects along.

PRE-WORKSHOP #1: MACHINE LEARNING FOR DESIGN, OPTIMIZATION & SEARCH

Facilitator: Zeynep Aksöy (IOA Vienna)

A quick assessment of all kinds of building performances is a pressing need in early design stages. This workshop examines how architects and designers can use data from their own internal as external sources to negotiate between performative design and aesthetic objectives through Machine Learning.

PRE-WORKSHOP #2: CONNECTING PROJECT & OFFICE SPECIFIC BUILDING MODELS WITH SPECKLE - OPEN SOURCE BIM COLLABORATION

Facilitator: Dimitrie Stefanescu (UCL), Paul Poinet (KADK)

The current proliferation of different design platforms make it difficult to share information easily within the building industry, as current digital design data is fragmented. This workshop puts forward the shared platform SPECKLE, through which different stakeholders can communicate and share information across design stages, thereby paving the way for a more inclusive design process

PRE-WORKSHOP #3: VIRTUAL CONSTRUCTION WITH ASSEMBLY INFORMATION MODELING

Facilitator: Ayoub Lharchi (KADK)

While digital tools support architects, engineers and constructors in almost all aspects of design and manufacturing, the planning and design for the assembly of buildings takes only place in late stages of design. This workshop will introduce an approach to represent, simulate, visualize, communicate and optimize assembly processes and data called "Assembly Information Modeling".

EVALUATION

Some numbers highlight the success of the Innochain conference

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

In total 208 tickets have been sold for the conference, with an even split of professional and student tickets for Master and PhD level attendees.

We welcomed attendees from 14 countries.

PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE VS ACADEMIA

The conference achieved an even mix of attendance from professional practice and academia. 32% of participants are currently employed in professional practices. 32% of attendees are researchers on senior and junior level at Universities. And 36% of participants have been Master students.

49 different companies situated in 8 different countries have been represented at the conference.

TEACHING ENVIRONMENTS

25 different European schools stemming from 11 different countries have been represented at the Innochain conference.

GENDER

The conference had 40% female attendees (83 female/ 125 male), which is way above the representation of women in the construction workforce (8% on EU level in 2007²) and the architectural profession (31% on EU level in 2010³).

² POWELL, ABIGAIL & HASSAN, TAREK & DAINTY, ANDREW & CARTER, CHRIS. (2007). STRENGTHENING WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN CONSTRUCTION RESEARCH IN EUROPE.

³ ARCHITECTS' COUNCIL OF EUROPE. THE ARCHITECTURAL PROFESSION IN EUROPE 2010. http://oar.archi/download/public/ace_sector_study_2010_en_pdf_1478000288.pdf

FIG. TOP The night of the Innocchain Conference saw a reception for all participants in the Innocchain exhibition.

FIG. The reception provided a space to thank the organisers, industry partners and all the Innochain ESRs for their efforts and enthusiasm.

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FIG. TOP Reception for all conference participants in the Innochain exhibition.

TECHNOLOGY IN ARCHITECTURE & DESIGN

CONFERENCE

EXPANDING INFORMATION MODELLING FOR A NEW MATERIAL AGE

Organized by Innochain

08-09/11 - BLOX

The conference questions how information modelling allows for new ways to think, design and build architecture.

With an international outlook, the conference examines the new digital platform, in which otherwise separate tools and methodologies of design, analysis and fabrication intersect.

innochain

TALKS

SOFTWARE IS EATING THE WORLD

Towards a computational design and architectural praxis?

15/11 - Auditorium 2, 15-17

Moderator: Martin Sønderlev Christensen

How can design and architectural praxis critically and constructively contribute to the digital transformation of our everyday life and lived environments?

THE END OF CURRENT PRACTICE

Can technology save the building industry?

20/11 - Auditorium 2, 15-17

Moderator: Natalie Mossin

What role can advanced technologies play in raising the level of innovation in the building and design industries - towards a sustainable future?

FROM CITYSWIPE TO SOCIAL CREDITS

Shaping the technological city

30/11 - Auditorium 2, 15-17

Moderator: Boris Broman Jensen

The talk raises the question of the role of designers and architects in the development of a pervasive digital infrastructure and offers a critical perspective on our use of technologies.

DIGITAL FABRICATION AS A DRIVER FOR SUSTAINABLE DESIGN INNOVATION

06/12 - Auditorium 2, 15-17

Moderator: Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen

Digital technologies are transforming existing paradigms of production in new distributed and democratized ways. How can quick prototyping and access to small batch production create new perspectives for industrial production?

The Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts
Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation

08.11
06.12.18

DANNESKJOLD-SAMSOES ALLÉ 51
1451 CPH K - FOR INFORMATION: KADK.DK

LOCAL SPIN OFF EVENTS

DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY

SEMINARS

ORGANISED BY:

Thomas Chevalier Bøjstrup (KADK)

Susanne Jøker Johnsen (KADK)

The Innochain Exhibition "Practice Futures: Building Design For A New Material Age" created the framework for a series of Spin-off projects, as the Innochain conference at BLOX and a series of talks on "Technology in Architecture and Design" at the The Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts, Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation (KADK) in Copenhagen.

Under the curatorship of Thomas Chevalier Bøjstrup and Susanne Jøker Johnsen, KADK invited students, staff, collaborators and the public to participate in a series of seminars.

Each of these was hosted and moderated by key profiles from the school of design and the school of architecture - each with a specific perspective on the theme. The moderators have each invited a number of speakers - from researchers to business and organizations - to present their ideas and debate with the audience. The talks created a platform within KADK to present and discuss different perspectives and foreseen roles of technology in relation to the profession, educational methods and roles in theoretical and practice based frameworks. The public exchange about these in the seminars with invited local and international guests sharpened the common profile and vision at KADK.

SEMINAR #1:

SOFTWARE IS EATING THE WORLD - Towards a Computational Design and Architectural Praxis?

15.11.2018 1500-1700

Host: Martin Sønderlev Christensen, Head of the Institute of Visual Design, KADK

Panel:

- Anna Vallgård, PhD, Associate Professor and Head of IxD Lab, IT UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN
- Christian Willum, Director of Digital & Future Thinking, DDC
- Martin Tamke, Associate Professor CITA Centre for Information Technology and Architecture, KADK

How can design and architectural praxis critically and constructively contribute to the digital transformation of our everyday life and lived environments?

In 2011 the American investor and entrepreneur Marc Andressen famously said that "Software is eating the world" proclaiming a broader economic and technological shift, where software companies are taking over as the driving force in the economy - rewriting the rules and value chains across industries. Obviously design and architecture is being eaten by software - offering new possibilities as well as challenging the existing praxis. We are increasingly moving from a traditional design praxis, towards a more computational driven design era, where computational processes are becoming an integral part of how and what we work with as designers and architects be it visual design, games, product design to architectural planning and constructions.

In this panel we will address how software is becoming a more integral part of our praxis. We will be asking what is software offering and what challenges does it pose. What characterizes computational design? How are concepts like machine learning and AI influencing how and what designers and architects work with? What can data provide as an opportunity for creating more intelligent and informed design process and products? How is computational modeling becoming a part of the creative process and to our design proposals? What are concepts like IoT and the embedding of computer power in our lived environments posing as opportunities and challenges? How is technological shift shaping the value chains, business models and service layers that design and architecture are conditioned in.

And also, how do we as architects and designers bite back when software is eating our trade? What important role could we play in a more critical and aesthetical stance in the dawning “techlash” towards the disruption of software and technology companies? How can we ensure that what often is sold “smart” not imposes new unintended consequences and behavior at the end-users? What are the new competences, roles and attitudes that we as designers and architects need to take on in a technological and increasingly digitized world?

SEMINAR #2:

THE END OF CURRENT PRACTICE-

Can technology save the building industry?

20.11.2018 1500-1700

Host: Natalie Mossin, Head of the Institute of Building Design and Technology

Panel:

- Jørgen Rosted, Consultant and writer. Cand.polit., Economics, Member of Danish Design Council and columnist, speaker and debater about e.g. green transition, innovation, entrepreneurship and finance.
- Phil Ayres, Associate Professor CITA Centre for Information Technology and Architecture, KADK
- Liselott Stenfeldt, Head of Interactive Spaces Urban Studio - Architect MAA Interactive Spaces Lab, The Alexandra Institute

The UN 17 Sustainable Developments Goals encapsulate what we must achieve, and the challenges are daunting. Architecture and design are fields of invention and entrepreneurship, and with the digitalization of design and manufacture a whole new set of opportunities are opening up.

But will new technology propel the industry forward towards more sustainable practices Can technology save the building industry At the talk we will discuss what role advanced technologies can play in raising the level of innovation in the building and design industries - towards a sustainable future.

SEMINAR #3:

FROM CITYSWIPE TO SOCIAL CREDITS - Shaping the technological city

30.11.2018 1500-1700

Host:

Boris Brorman Jensen - Associate Professor, Institute for Building Design and Design

Panel

- Jeff Risom, Partner, Chief Innovation Officer, MSc City Design & Social Sciences. Gehl architects
- Deane Alan Simpson, Professor, D.Sc. (Doctor of Science) (ETH Zürich), Institute of Architecture, Urbanism and Landscape, The Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts, Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation.

The talk raises the question of the role of designers and architects in the development of a pervasive digital infrastructure and offers a critical perspective on our use of technologies.

What does the technologists' city look like? Building cities has moved from an architectural process to largely a technological experiment. Architecture and design has expanded beyond the form and beauty of buildings to shape our everyday physical and social experiences. In this way, technology in cities can play a major role in defining citizenship, changing political power dynamics through catalytic social movements, and understanding human behavior to invite for connections that promote empathy.

Smart City – Post-Political Utopia? While technology (companies) offer a neo-modernist wave of urban techno-rationalization, efficiency, and 'convenience' – with obvious and apparent advantages – could it be that the 'smart-city' as it is currently rolled out in settings such as Toronto, Rio or London, represents a critical challenge to the role of the architect/planner; to the 'right to the city' of the urban citizen; and to future of the urban realm as a political space

SEMINAR #4:

DIGITAL FABRICATION AS A DRIVER FOR SUSTAINABLE DESIGN INNOVATION- Additive Manufacturing Future

06.12.2018 1500-1700

Host:

Professor Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen, Head of the Centre for Information Technology and Architecture, KADK

Panel:

- "3D Printing Recycled Clay" Alexandre Dubor, Robotic Expert, IAAC, MRAC Director, OTF Co-director, MAA, MAI, OTF Senior Faculty
- "3D printing wood" Ambra Trotto, Studio Director, RISE Interactive, Research Institutes of Sweden
- "3D printing ceramics" Martin Tamke, Associate Professor CITA Centre for Information Technology and Architecture, KADK and Flemming Tvede Hansen, Associate Professor, Architecture and Design, KADK
- "Future of Additive Manufacture" Mads Kjøller Damkjær, CEO Director, Danish AM Hub

Digital technologies are transforming existing paradigms of production in new distributed and democratized ways. How can quick prototyping and access to small batch production create new perspectives for industrial production

Digital technologies are transforming existing paradigms of production in new distributed and democratized ways. How can quick prototyping and access to small batch production create new perspectives for industrial production

Digitization is transforming existing paradigms of production, making it easier to collaborate and communicate in distributed and democratized ways. Cheap new technologies enable developing countries and markets to leapfrog creating broader access to knowledge and reach further to new audiences while changing industrial fabrication from something only in the remit of the few to a broader culture of prototyping and small batch production. With examples from around world, we will discuss new perspectives on digital empowerment; what are the new products and services that these processes enable, how do we empower innovation in new economic models for growth and how does this practice create new perspectives for social empowerment.

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04

PRE-VIVA SEMINAR

**STRATEGIC FEEDBACK FOR
STRONG WRITE-UP PLANS**

PRE- VIVA SEMINARS

PERSON TO PERSON & ONLINE
FEBRUARY - APRIL 2018
ITKE (RICCARDO LA MANGA, JAN KNIPPERS)

As part of the Innochain curricular activities, a series of training events were organized with the scope of providing the ESRs information and guidance on the writing of their doctoral theses. The aim of the seminars was to help the ESRs to find the right model for their PhD works and to ensure that a high-quality level was met across the range of PhDs of the Innochain program. Four Previva Seminars took place between February and May 2018, divided between lectures on good practice of writing and the review of work provided by the candidates.

LEFT: RICCARDO LA MAGNA

RIGHT: Jan Knippers

PRE-VIVA SEMINAR #1 - FEBRUARY 2018:

The first seminar took place during the Second Innochain Colloquium In Barcelona in February 2018. It was focused on giving the ESRs a general introduction on the scopes and aims of a doctoral work. Particular emphasis was given to the framing of the scientific context and the state of the art as a necessary preliminary step to pin down the relevance of each individual work. The discussion was complemented by the presentation and discussion of well-structured PhD theses brought by the supervisors. The candidates were able in this way to confront and discuss the works directly with the supervisors and get feedback on the process of structuring a doctoral thesis.

PRE-VIVA SEMINAR #2 - MARCH 2018:

The second seminar on 7th March 2018 was centred on the conceptual organization of a doctoral work. Different examples of PhD organizational flowcharts were presented and discussed with the ESRs. Specific attention was spent on analysing and reviewing the conceptual framework a doctoral work is built upon, with emphasis on the aim and scope of the work, as well as the review of the state of the art. Citation styles and good practice for citing and quoting other works as well as own work was discussed in depth. Finally, the seminar was complemented by practical suggestions and general advices about the actual redaction of a PhD thesis, presenting text

PRE-VIVA SEMINAR #3 - APRIL 2018:

Based on the topics presented in the previous seminars, the ESRs were asked to start organizing their scientific work in conceptual flowcharts. These were presented by the candidates during an online session on 5th April 2018 and jointly reviewed by Prof. Dr.-Ing. Jan Knippers and Dr.-Ing. Riccardo La Magna (ITKE). The individual flowcharts were discussed and analysed in detail, specifically providing feedback on the organization of the material.

PRE-VIVA SEMINAR #4 - MAY 2018:

Based on the feedback provided during the last seminar, the ESRs reviewed their conceptual flowcharts with their respective supervisors and updated it accordingly. In the final session of the previva seminar series on 17th May, the reviewed and reorganized works were presented by the ESRs along with a preliminary timeline of the expected work development.

The seminars gave the candidates the possibility to start structuring their scientific work in an organic manner around conceptual flowcharts. The review and discussion of these flowcharts by a panel of external experts along with the individual supervisors, gave the ESRs the opportunity to get active feedback on the development and advancement of their work.

EXAMPLE OF FLOWCHART. FROM: SCHLEICHER S., **BIO-INSPIRED COMPLIANT MECHANISMS FOR ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN – TRANSFERRING BENDING AND FOLDING PRINCIPLES OF PLANT LEAVES TO FLEXIBLE KINETIC STRUCTURES**, 2015, PH.D. THESIS

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05

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The InnoChain Exhibition and Conference wouldn't have been possible without the contribution of all ESRs, Members of the Innochain Supervisor Board, the industry partners and involved institutions.

A special thanks to Susan Jøker Johnson (KADK), who has been instrumental for the design, organisation and curatorship of the exhibition and Yuliya Sinke (CITA) for her enduring contribution to both the Exhibition and Conference. We as well want to thank the team from BLOXhub for their sparring during the conference design phase and their support in its conduction. Finally a big thank you to all CITA studio students of the year 2018/2019, who were instrumental in the setup and operation of the exhibition and conference.

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